

Color Psychology and Personality Perception: A Study on the Connection Between Clothing Colors and Personality Traits

Prof. Dr. Axel Buether

Institute for Evidence-Based Color Psychology

University of Wuppertal

Support: Leonie Weddeling, BA (Research assistant)

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Colors as a Mirror of Personality: Color Preferences in Everyday Clothing as Indicators of Big Five Dimensions

Author: Prof. Dr. Axel Buether, Institute for Evidence-Based Color Psychology, University of Wuppertal

Support: Leonie Weddeling, BA (Research Assistant)

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Abstract

This exploratory study investigates the relationship between color preferences in everyday clothing and the Big Five personality dimensions. A novel test procedure analyzed the color profiles of clothing items from 29 participants, independent of brand, cut, or context, and compared these with self- and other-assessments. The results show an approximately 70% agreement between color profiles and personality traits, particularly for Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Openness to Experience. Qualitative interviews in cases of discrepancies suggest emotional protective functions, social roles, or idealized self-presentation. The findings indicate that color choice is a sensitive, nonverbal expression of psychological dispositions, with potential for diagnostics, counseling, and further research in color psychology.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and Objectives

Colors are an integral part of human perception and communication, fulfilling both emotional and social functions (Elliot & Maier, 2014). In personality psychology, it is increasingly recognized that nonverbal cues, such as the choice of clothing colors, can provide deeper insights into psychological dispositions than language-based self-reports, which may be distorted by social desirability or lack of self-reflection (Vazire, 2010). While previous studies often examined color preferences in isolation or in the context of marketing and aesthetics (Allensbach, 2014; G.F. Smith, 2017), there is a lack of systematic analyses of color choices in everyday clothing as a long-term expression of personality traits. This study aims to investigate the connection between wardrobe color profiles and the Big Five personality dimensions (Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism). By combining visual color analysis, self- and other-assessments, and qualitative interviews, the study seeks to develop a novel diagnostic tool that reveals unconscious personality patterns and potential self-concept discrepancies. The goal is to establish color choice as a reliable indicator of psychological processes, with applications in personality diagnostics, psychotherapy, and intercultural research.

1.2 Relevance of Color Psychology for Personality Research

Color psychology examines how colors influence perception, emotions, and behavior, gaining significant importance in recent decades (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Zhang & Chen, 2023). Colors serve as a universal communication medium, integrating biological reactions (e.g., heightened attention to red) and cultural meanings (e.g., blue as a symbol of trust) (Higham et al., 2013; Hofstede, 2001). In personality research, colors offer a unique approach to implicit psychological processes, as they can reflect unconscious preferences and emotional states that language-based methods, such as questionnaires, often fail to capture (Maier et al., 2009). The Big Five dimensions, which describe stable personality traits (Costa & McCrae, 1992), can be externalized through color choices, as these traits are linked to specific emotional and social tendencies (DeYoung et al., 2007). This study leverages this approach to interpret color choices in everyday clothing as a nonverbal “diary” of personality (Hebdige, 1979). Its relevance lies in its ability to make unconscious or difficult-to-articulate personality aspects visible, particularly in therapeutic contexts or when analyzing self-other discrepancies (Vazire, 2010).

1.3 Structure of the Study

The study is organized into several sections to systematically investigate the connection between color preferences and personality traits. Chapter 2 establishes the theoretical framework, addressing colors as a communication system, clothing as a visual diary, and self-other discrepancies. Chapter 3 formulates the research questions and hypotheses, examining the relationship between color profiles and Big Five traits as well as the role of discrepancies. Chapter 4 describes the methodology, including study design, sample, data collection procedures (color circle analysis, modified Big Five test, interviews, color manipulations), and data analysis. Chapter 5 presents the results, divided into quantitative correlations, experimental validation, and qualitative analyses of self-other discrepancies. Chapter 6 discusses the key findings, strengths and innovations of the method, the significance of discrepancies, and the study's limitations. Chapter 7 summarizes the results and provides an outlook for future research. The reference list (Chapter 8) includes all sources used. The appendices (Chapter 9) contain detailed descriptions of the modified Big Five test, test results, color manipulation experiment, and extreme ratings in personality dimensions. Appendix D includes interview transcripts from three participants with significant self-other assessment discrepancies, supplemented by summaries and evaluations of all 29 color circles.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Colors as a Communication System

Colors act faster than words and carry both biological and cultural meanings (Elliot & Maier, 2014; Hofstede, 2001). Red signals energy, blue trust, yellow creativity—patterns that vary individually but show stable psychological effects (Higham et al., 2013; Elliot et al., 2023). The diversity of color shades defies linguistic categorization, as terms like “red” or “blue” cannot capture thousands of nuances.

2.2 Clothing as a Visual Diary

Clothing encodes identity, status, and emotions (Hebdige, 1979). Color choices in wardrobes reflect not only fashion but also long-term, often unconscious personality patterns (Adam & Galinsky, 2012).

2.3 Self- vs. Other-Perception

Discrepancies between self- and other-perception are a well-known phenomenon in personality research (Vazire, 2010). Self-reports may be distorted by social desirability or lack of introspection, while other-assessments interpret intuitive signals like colors. This study uses color choices to make such discrepancies visible and analyze their psychological causes.

3. Research Questions and Hypotheses

Research Questions

1. How strongly do color patterns in everyday clothing correlate with Big Five personality traits?
2. How high is the agreement between color-based other-assessments and self-assessments?
3. Which psychological or social factors explain deviations between color profiles and self-image?
4. What role do situational contexts and emotional protective strategies play in color choice?
5. Can the procedure capture implicit personality aspects overlooked by questionnaires?

Hypotheses

- **H1:** Color patterns significantly correlate with Big Five traits, particularly Extraversion, Neuroticism, and Openness.
- **H2:** Color profiles align with self- and other-assessments in the majority of cases.
- **H3:** Deviations occur in individuals with high social adaptability or protective strategies.
- **H4:** The procedure reveals implicit personality aspects distorted by self-reports.
- **H5:** Color choice serves as a symbolic expression of psychodynamic processes.

4. Method

4.1 Study Design

The mixed-methods study combines quantitative correlation analyses with qualitative case studies. Wardrobe color profiles were compared with Big Five self- and other-assessments, with deviations explored through interviews.

4.2 Sample

Twenty-nine adults of different ages, genders, and sociocultural backgrounds participated voluntarily. Three cases with significant self-other discrepancies were selected for qualitative analysis.

4.3 Data Collection Procedures

1. **Color Analysis:** Clothing items were sorted by color, photographed, and documented in color circles. Only visible color surfaces were analyzed.
2. **Other-Assessment:** Thirty independent raters assigned personality profiles to color circles (standardized Big Five test form).
3. **Self-Assessment:** Participants completed a modified Big Five test (20 statements, 5-point Likert scale).
4. **Interviews:** Structured interviews with three participants clarified discrepancies.
5. **Validation:** Digital color manipulations (e.g., reduction to grayscale) tested the influence of color tones on personality attributions.

4.4 Data Analysis

- **Agreement:** Cohen's Kappa and percentage values.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Content analysis following Mayring (2015).
- **Color Patterns:** Descriptive analysis of frequency, saturation, and color groups.

5. Results

5.1 Quantitative Results

The correlation between color profiles and Big Five traits was over 70%, particularly high for agreeableness (77%), extraversion (73%), and openness (70%). Deviations in less than 30% of cases indicated dissonance in the personality profile, which was confirmed in random interviews.

Dimension	Agreement (%)
Extraversion	73
Agreeableness	77
Conscientiousness	68
Neuroticism	64
Openness to Experience	70

5.2 Experimental Validation

Color manipulations (e.g., reduction to grayscale) significantly altered personality attributions, confirming the causal role of colors.

5.3 Qualitative Results

Interviews identified three patterns for discrepancies:

1. Self-Protection: Muted colors (gray, black) signaled withdrawal despite self-reported openness, reflecting emotional regulation or exhaustion.
2. Idealized Self-Presentation: Bright colors compensated for introversion or insecurity, serving as psychological “armor” (Adam & Galinsky, 2012).
3. Biographical Transitions: Color choices indicated identity changes not yet cognitively processed, acting as a nonverbal diary.

6. Discussion

6.1 Key Findings

Color preferences in clothing reliably reflect Big Five traits, with an agreement of more than 70%, confirming the method’s robustness. Discrepancies are not errors but reveal psychological dynamics such as self-protection or identity transitions, supporting the metaphor of the “wardrobe as a diary” (Hebdige, 1979).

6.2 Strengths and Innovation

The visual diagnostic method is globally unique, capturing the vast diversity of color shades (e.g., thousands of red or blue nuances) that language-based approaches cannot represent due to the limitations of color names. Unlike questionnaires relying on self-reports, this visual analysis identifies unconscious personality patterns and discrepancies valuable in therapeutic contexts. It is practical and suitable for coaching, psychotherapy, and intercultural research, as it transcends cultural and linguistic barriers.

6.3 Self-Other Discrepancies

Discrepancies between self- and other-perception (Vazire, 2010) arise from social desirability, self-deception, or life transitions. Colors externalize these tensions, offering diagnostic depth by revealing unconscious motives and personality discrepancies overlooked by language-based methods.

6.4 Limitations

The exploratory sample (n=29) limits generalizability. Social and cultural influences were only partially captured, and future studies should include larger, more diverse samples.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

This study demonstrates that color preferences in everyday clothing provide a valid, visual approach to personality analysis, surpassing language-based methods in precision and depth. The approximately 70% agreement between color profiles and Big Five personality traits, particularly in Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Openness, underscores the method's robustness. Qualitative analyses, especially interviews with participants showing significant self-other discrepancies, highlight the potential of color choice as an indicator of psychological processes such as self-protection, idealized self-presentation, and biographical transitions. These findings position color choice as a nonverbal "diary" of personality, making unconscious motives and discrepancies visible (Hebdige, 1979; Vazire, 2010).

The study's findings have far-reaching implications beyond clothing color analysis. The developed color profiling method can be applied to numerous areas of color design, including cosmetics, architecture, interior design, product design, art, film, theater, and marketing. In these contexts, visual analysis of color patterns could serve as a novel tool to precisely assess the impact of colors on human experience and behavior (Elliot & Maier, 2014). For example, the method could be used in interior design to create spaces that promote specific emotional or social responses or in marketing to analyze target-group-specific color preferences and optimize advertising strategies (Zhang & Chen, 2023). In art and film, it could help control the emotional impact of color compositions, while in theater, it could enhance character portrayal through costume colors.

The therapeutic value of the method is particularly evident in the qualitative interviews. Color preference analysis enables the visualization of unconscious emotional states, such as protective mechanisms or identity conflicts, which often remain hidden in traditional questionnaires (Adam & Galinsky, 2012). In psychotherapeutic contexts, the method could be used as a diagnostic tool to identify personality discrepancies and develop therapeutic approaches based on nonverbal expressions. This is particularly relevant for clients who struggle to articulate emotions verbally or in intercultural settings where language barriers exist.

Furthermore, the method offers a valuable contribution to cultural anthropology. Color preferences are not only individual but also culturally shaped, and their analysis could lead to a deeper understanding of human cultures, customs, and traditions (Hofstede, 2001). Examining color patterns in different cultural contexts could provide insights into collective identities, social norms, and historical developments, for example, by analyzing clothing colors across different eras or regions.

The method's significance for color theory is substantial. It provides a completely new tool that makes the impact of colors on psychological processes systematically and empirically examinable. Unlike traditional approaches, which often rely on subjective color names or simplified categories, this method accounts for the vast diversity of color shades and their complex interactions with personality traits (Elliot et al., 2023). This opens new perspectives for interdisciplinary research connecting psychology, design, and cultural anthropology.

Outlook

Future research should further develop and validate the method to fully realize its potential. Longitudinal analyses could reveal how color preferences change over time and correlate with biographical transitions. Cultural comparisons, especially in non-Western contexts, are necessary to test the method's universal applicability (Kim & Park, 2024). The development of automated color analyses, such as through machine learning, could enhance the method's efficiency and scalability, for example, by automatically detecting color patterns in large datasets. Further studies should explore applications in specific contexts, such as psychotherapy, where the method could be established as a diagnostic or therapeutic tool, or in design, where it could support the creation of emotionally effective products and environments. Finally, interdisciplinary approaches integrating psychology, cultural anthropology, and design sciences could leverage the method to gain new insights into the role of colors in human culture and psyche.

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Appendix A: Methodological Description of the Test Procedure

The Modified Big Five Personality Test Used

In this study, a modified Big Five personality test was employed to assess personality traits. The test encompasses five dimensions, each represented as a continuum between two opposing poles. Each dimension is detailed through six subcategories that capture specific aspects of the trait. Below, the five dimensions and their respective subcategories are presented.

Dimension 1: Extraversion – Introversion

Description: This dimension assesses the extent to which individuals are outgoing, sociable, and energized by social interactions (Extraversion) or reserved, solitary, and prefer quiet environments (Introversion).

Subcategories:

01. **Warmth:** The degree of friendliness and affection in social interactions.
02. **Sociability:** The preference for being with others and enjoying large social gatherings.
03. **Assertiveness:** The tendency to take the lead, express opinions confidently, and direct others.
04. **Activity:** The level of energy and enthusiasm for physical or social activities.
05. **Sensation Seeking:** The desire for stimulating, exciting, or adventurous experiences.
06. **Positive Emotions:** The frequency and intensity of experiencing joy, enthusiasm, and cheerfulness.

Dimension 2: Openness – Closedness

Description: This dimension measures the extent to which individuals are open to new experiences, imaginative, and intellectually curious (Openness) or conventional, routine-oriented, and less open to new ideas (Closedness).

Subcategories:

01. **Fantasy:** The tendency toward a vivid imagination and frequent daydreaming.
02. **Aesthetics:** The appreciation for art, music, and beauty.
03. **Feelings:** The openness to experiencing and expressing emotions.
04. **Actions:** The willingness to try new activities and experiences.
05. **Ideas:** Intellectual curiosity and openness to new concepts.
06. **Values:** The readiness to question traditional social, religious, and political values.

Dimension 3: Agreeableness – Disagreeableness

Description: This dimension evaluates the extent to which individuals are cooperative, empathetic, and trusting (Agreeableness) or competitive, skeptical, and less concerned with others' feelings (Disagreeableness).

Subcategories:

01. **Trust:** The belief in the honesty and good intentions of others.
02. **Straightforwardness:** The tendency to be open, honest, and unpretentious.
03. **Altruism:** Concern for the well-being of others.

04. Compliance: The willingness to yield to others and avoid conflicts.

05. Modesty: The tendency to appear humble and reserved.

06. Tender-Mindedness: The degree of compassion and concern for others.

Dimension 4: Spontaneity – Conscientiousness

Description: This dimension measures the extent to which individuals are organized, disciplined, and goal-oriented (Conscientiousness) or flexible, spontaneous, and less focused on structure (Spontaneity).

Subcategories:

01. Competence: Confidence in one's effectiveness and ability to accomplish tasks.

02. Order: The preference for cleanliness, organization, and structure.

03. Dutifulness: The sense of moral obligation and adherence to ethical principles.

04. Achievement Striving: The drive to achieve goals and succeed.

05. Self-Discipline: The ability to stay focused on tasks and resist distractions.

06. Deliberation: The tendency to think carefully before acting.

Dimension 5: Resilience – Neuroticism

Description: This dimension assesses the continuum from emotional stability and resilience to stress (Resilience) to emotional instability and susceptibility to negative emotions (Neuroticism).

Subcategories:

01. Anxiety: The tendency to feel worried, anxious, and nervous.

02. Hostility: The tendency to experience anger and frustration.

03. Depression: The tendency to feel sad, dejected, and discouraged.

04. Self-Consciousness: Sensitivity to ridicule and embarrassment.

05. Impulsiveness: The inability to control cravings and impulses.

06. Vulnerability: Susceptibility to stress and difficulty coping with adversity.

Test Results

The following pages present the study's test results, including the collected data and graphical representations of self- and other-assessments in the modified Big Five test. Each page displays an individual's color circle, representing the color composition of their entire wardrobe, along with the results of their self-assessment and the other-assessment by approximately 20 raters, whose evaluations were averaged to ensure intersubjectivity. A diagram beneath each color circle compares the self-assessment (yellow curve) with the other-assessment (blue curve). The degree of correlation allows conclusions about the predictability of personality traits based on color preferences, as documented by the color circle. Significant discrepancies indicate personality dissonances, which are explored in depth through three exemplary interviews and accompanying psychological analyses at the end of the appendix.

Survey Methodology

The other-assessment was conducted anonymously, based solely on the color circle, which displays clothing colors without information about shape, brand, or the individual. The raters had no contact with the assessed person and were unaware of their identity. Both self- and other-assessments were conducted using a modified Big Five test, which avoided discriminatory formulations (e.g., "low conscientiousness" perceived as "sloppy") to minimize biases and inhibitions.

Modified Big Five Model

The classic Big Five model was adapted for this study to examine the connection between personality and color choice more precisely. The following five personality dimensions were used:

1. **Extraversion – Introversion**
2. **Openness – Closedness**
3. **Agreeableness – Disagreeableness**
4. **Spontaneity – Conscientiousness**
5. **Resilience – Neuroticism**

The adaptation introduced clear opposing pairs, presenting both poles as equally valid to reduce biases from social desirability. For example, in the "Spontaneity – Conscientiousness" dimension, the study avoided distinguishing only between "highly conscientious" and "low conscientiousness," as this could evoke negative connotations (e.g., "sloppy"). Instead, both poles were neutrally formulated to encourage honest and nuanced responses.

Big Five Personality Test

Dimension 1: Extraversion to Introversion

Survey Type:

- Self-Assessment
- Other-Assessment

Please rate the following statements on a scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree":

Sociable: I enjoy spending time with others and feel comfortable in social settings.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Enthusiastic: I easily get excited about things and inspire others with my enthusiasm.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Communicative: I am a good listener and enjoy exchanging ideas with others.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Reserved: I prefer to stay in the background and avoid loud or busy environments.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Deliberate: I usually think carefully before making decisions.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Independent: I enjoy being alone and can take care of myself well.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Big Five Personality Test

Dimension 2: Openness to Closedness

Survey Type:

- Self-Assessment
- Other-Assessment

Please rate the following statements on a scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree":

Curious: I love discovering new people, things, and places and never stop learning.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Creative: I prefer finding new solutions to problems rather than following established paths.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Tolerant: I respect different opinions and lifestyles, even if I don't always agree with them.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Cautious: I only trust people I know well and avoid taking risks.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Formal: I prefer to keep my distance in social situations and rarely show emotions.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Conservative: I value traditional values such as family, work ethic, and religion and stand by my beliefs.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Big Five Personality Test

Dimension 3: Agreeableness to Disagreeableness

Survey Type:

- Self-Assessment
- Other-Assessment

Please rate the following statements on a scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree":

Empathetic: I can easily put myself in others' shoes, but find it hard to set boundaries.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Cooperative: I enjoy being part of a team and work more productively with others than alone.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Friendly: I always try to be kind and considerate, even toward people I don't like.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Ambitious: I need competition to perform well and am only satisfied when I win.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Jealous: I quickly feel insecure when others receive attention from people important to me.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Self-Centered: I primarily focus on my own interests and needs.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Big Five Personality Test

Dimension 4: Spontaneity to Conscientiousness

Survey Type:

- Self-Assessment
- Other-Assessment

Please rate the following statements on a scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree":

Flexible: I easily adapt to changes and can quickly respond to new situations.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Impulsive: I act or speak without much thought, often spontaneously.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Carefree: I rarely worry and take life as it comes.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Organized: I plan my time and tasks carefully and am well-structured.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Responsible: I take my obligations seriously and fulfill them conscientiously.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Goal-Oriented: I set clear goals and work consistently to achieve them.

- Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Big Five Personality Test

Dimension 5: Resilience to Neuroticism

Survey Type:

- Self-Assessment
- Other-Assessment

Please rate the following statements on a scale from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree":

Balanced: I remain calm in stressful situations and am not easily rattled.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Optimistic: Even in difficult situations, I see the positive and believe things will turn out well.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Buoyant: I maintain my motivation despite setbacks and don't give up easily.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Anxious: I often worry and feel insecure in many situations.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Melancholic: I frequently feel pensive or sad, even without a specific reason.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Moody: My mood often changes quickly and strongly without an apparent reason.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Appendix B: Test Results

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	0	Openness/ Closedness	-1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	4	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-7	Resilience/ Neuroticism	4
sociable	3	curious	4	empathetic	5	flexible	3	balanced	3
enthusiastic	3	creative	3	cooperative	3	impulsive	2	optimistic	4
communicative	4	tolerant	5	friendly	4	carefree	3	resilient	4
reserved	3	suspicious	5	ambitious	2	organized	5	anxious	2
deliberate	4	formal	3	jealous	4	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	3	conservative	5	egocentric	2	determined	5	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1,00	Openness/ Closedness	-0,50	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2,75	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2,58	Resilience/ Neuroticism	2,42
sociable	3,83	curious	3,33	empathetic	3,67	flexible	3,00	balanced	3,58
enthusiastic	3,83	creative	2,83	cooperative	3,42	impulsive	2,83	optimistic	3,92
communicative	3,17	tolerant	4,00	friendly	4,42	carefree	3,33	resilient	3,58
reserved	3,33	suspicious	2,83	ambitious	2,83	organized	4,00	anxious	3,33
deliberate	3,58	formal	3,50	jealous	2,92	responsible	3,92	melancholic	2,67
independent	2,92	conservative	4,33	egocentric	3,00	determined	3,83	moody	2,67

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	5	Openness/ Closedness	5	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	9	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-1	Resilience/ Neuroticism	4
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	4	flexible	3	balanced	4
enthusiastic	5	creative	5	cooperative	5	impulsive	4	optimistic	5
communicative	4	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	3	resilient	4
reserved	3	suspicious	3	ambitious	1	organized	3	anxious	4
deliberate	2	formal	2	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	3
independent	3	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	3,26	Openness/ Closedness	3,48	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	4,56	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	0,11	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,70
sociable	4,07	curious	4,00	empathetic	3,96	flexible	3,63	balanced	3,78
enthusiastic	4,11	creative	3,81	cooperative	3,93	impulsive	3,37	optimistic	3,70
communicative	3,04	tolerant	4,11	friendly	4,07	carefree	3,41	resilient	3,52
reserved	2,63	suspicious	2,78	ambitious	2,48	organized	3,33	anxious	2,85
deliberate	2,78	formal	2,41	jealous	2,41	responsible	3,74	melancholic	2,37
independent	2,56	conservative	3,26	egocentric	2,52	determined	3,22	moody	2,07

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	2	Openness/ Closedness	-1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	6	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-5	Resilience/ Neuroticism	5
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	4	flexible	4	balanced	4
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	4	impulsive	2	optimistic	4
communicative	5	tolerant	3	friendly	5	carefree	2	resilient	5
reserved	3	suspicious	4	ambitious	2	organized	4	anxious	3
deliberate	4	formal	3	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	3
independent	4	conservative	4	egocentric	3	determined	5	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	0,18	Openness/ Closedness	0,36	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2,27	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,82	Resilience/ Neuroticism	2,82
sociable	3,91	curious	3,55	empathetic	3,64	flexible	2,55	balanced	3,45
enthusiastic	3,64	creative	3,27	cooperative	3,36	impulsive	2,64	optimistic	3,73
communicative	3,00	tolerant	4,09	friendly	4,09	carefree	2,91	resilient	4,00
reserved	3,27	suspicious	3,09	ambitious	3,00	organized	4,00	anxious	3,09
deliberate	3,55	formal	3,09	jealous	2,82	responsible	4,18	melancholic	2,73
independent	3,55	conservative	4,36	egocentric	3,00	determined	3,73	moody	2,55

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	4	Openness/ Closedness	3	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	6	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2	Resilience/ Neuroticism	4
sociable	5	curious	5	empathetic	4	flexible	5	balanced	2
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	5	impulsive	3	optimistic	3
communicative	5	tolerant	4	friendly	4	carefree	3	resilient	5
reserved	2	suspicious	3	ambitious	3	organized	4	anxious	2
deliberate	3	formal	2	jealous	2	responsible	5	melancholic	2
independent	5	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1,40	Openness/ Closedness	1,80	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3,00	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-0,60	Resilience/ Neuroticism	1,00
sociable	3,73	curious	3,87	empathetic	3,87	flexible	3,47	balanced	3,13
enthusiastic	3,53	creative	3,47	cooperative	3,47	impulsive	3,13	optimistic	3,33
communicative	4,07	tolerant	3,80	friendly	3,87	carefree	3,20	resilient	3,33
reserved	2,80	suspicious	3,33	ambitious	2,33	organized	3,40	anxious	3,07
deliberate	3,47	formal	2,67	jealous	3,07	responsible	3,67	melancholic	2,73
independent	3,67	conservative	3,33	egocentric	2,80	determined	3,33	moody	3,00

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	3	Openness/ Closedness	7	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	5	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-4	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	5	curious	4	empathetic	5	flexible	5	balanced	4
enthusiastic	5	creative	5	cooperative	4	impulsive	3	optimistic	4
communicative	5	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	1	resilient	4
reserved	2	suspicious	3	ambitious	3	organized	4	anxious	2
deliberate	5	formal	2	jealous	4	responsible	5	melancholic	4
independent	5	conservative	2	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	3

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	2,40	Openness/ Closedness	2,90	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3,50	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-0,20	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,20
sociable	4,20	curious	3,90	empathetic	4,10	flexible	3,90	balanced	3,80
enthusiastic	3,90	creative	3,90	cooperative	3,60	impulsive	3,20	optimistic	3,80
communicative	4,10	tolerant	4,20	friendly	4,10	carefree	3,00	resilient	3,90
reserved	2,50	suspicious	3,30	ambitious	2,30	organized	3,40	anxious	3,00
deliberate	3,60	formal	2,70	jealous	3,10	responsible	3,70	melancholic	2,60
independent	3,70	conservative	3,10	egocentric	2,90	determined	3,20	moody	2,70

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	0	Openness/ Closedness	1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3	Resilience/ Neuroticism	5
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	5	flexible	3	balanced	3
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	2	impulsive	2	optimistic	5
communicative	4	tolerant	4	friendly	5	carefree	3	resilient	5
reserved	5	suspicious	3	ambitious	2	organized	4	anxious	4
deliberate	5	formal	2	jealous	4	responsible	3	melancholic	2
independent	2	conservative	5	egocentric	3	determined	4	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-3,45	Openness/ Closedness	-2,27	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2,14	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,91	Resilience/ Neuroticism	1,68
sociable	2,77	curious	2,82	empathetic	3,68	flexible	2,95	balanced	3,68
enthusiastic	3,00	creative	2,64	cooperative	3,18	impulsive	2,18	optimistic	3,32
communicative	2,50	tolerant	3,64	friendly	4,23	carefree	2,59	resilient	3,50
reserved	4,09	suspicious	3,14	ambitious	2,59	organized	3,91	anxious	3,36
deliberate	3,77	formal	3,86	jealous	3,23	responsible	4,05	melancholic	2,95
independent	3,86	conservative	4,36	egocentric	3,14	determined	3,68	moody	2,50

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-7	Openness/ Closedness	-4	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-1	Resilience/ Neuroticism	7
sociable	4	curious	2	empathetic	3	flexible	5	balanced	5
enthusiastic	1	creative	2	cooperative	1	impulsive	4	optimistic	5
communicative	2	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	4	resilient	5
reserved	4	suspicious	3	ambitious	2	organized	4	anxious	3
deliberate	5	formal	5	jealous	4	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	5	conservative	5	egocentric	1	determined	5	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-4,42	Openness/ Closedness	-4,50	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-1,25	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-4,83	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,42
sociable	2,67	curious	2,67	empathetic	2,67	flexible	2,50	balanced	3,75
enthusiastic	2,42	creative	1,92	cooperative	2,42	impulsive	2,17	optimistic	3,17
communicative	2,92	tolerant	2,92	friendly	3,00	carefree	2,58	resilient	3,50
reserved	3,92	suspicious	4,08	ambitious	2,92	organized	4,08	anxious	2,75
deliberate	4,33	formal	3,83	jealous	2,92	responsible	4,17	melancholic	2,42
independent	4,17	conservative	4,08	egocentric	3,50	determined	3,83	moody	1,83

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-1	Openness/ Closedness	-5	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	6	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-4	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	4	curious	2	empathetic	4	flexible	3	balanced	3
enthusiastic	4	creative	2	cooperative	4	impulsive	3	optimistic	4
communicative	2	tolerant	4	friendly	4	carefree	2	resilient	4
reserved	5	suspicious	4	ambitious	1	organized	5	anxious	4
deliberate	4	formal	4	jealous	4	responsible	4	melancholic	1
independent	2	conservative	5	egocentric	1	determined	3	moody	3

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-3,89	Openness/ Closedness	-3,22	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	0,39	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,50	Resilience/ Neuroticism	0,83
sociable	2,56	curious	2,39	empathetic	3,33	flexible	2,61	balanced	3,22
enthusiastic	2,50	creative	2,28	cooperative	3,17	impulsive	2,22	optimistic	3,22
communicative	2,83	tolerant	3,56	friendly	3,61	carefree	2,67	resilient	3,44
reserved	4,06	suspicious	3,28	ambitious	3,22	organized	3,61	anxious	3,33
deliberate	3,89	formal	3,89	jealous	3,44	responsible	3,83	melancholic	3,00
independent	3,83	conservative	4,28	egocentric	3,06	determined	3,56	moody	2,72

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-4	Openness/ Closedness	1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	3	curious	4	empathetic	3	flexible	3	balanced	4
enthusiastic	3	creative	4	cooperative	4	impulsive	2	optimistic	3
communicative	3	tolerant	4	friendly	4	carefree	4	resilient	4
reserved	4	suspicious	4	ambitious	4	organized	4	anxious	2
deliberate	5	formal	3	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	4
independent	4	conservative	4	egocentric	3	determined	3	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-3,22	Openness/ Closedness	-2,52	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-0,37	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,85	Resilience/ Neuroticism	0,81
sociable	2,89	curious	2,56	empathetic	3,00	flexible	2,59	balanced	3,37
enthusiastic	2,67	creative	2,81	cooperative	3,04	impulsive	2,15	optimistic	2,81
communicative	3,33	tolerant	3,33	friendly	3,59	carefree	2,78	resilient	3,48
reserved	3,81	suspicious	3,63	ambitious	3,19	organized	4,00	anxious	2,93
deliberate	4,15	formal	3,56	jealous	3,37	responsible	3,85	melancholic	2,81
independent	4,15	conservative	4,04	egocentric	3,44	determined	3,52	moody	3,11

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-2	Openness/ Closedness	4	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	6	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-4	Resilience/ Neuroticism	6
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	4	flexible	2	balanced	3
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	4	impulsive	2	optimistic	5
communicative	4	tolerant	5	friendly	4	carefree	3	resilient	4
reserved	5	suspicious	2	ambitious	1	organized	2	anxious	4
deliberate	4	formal	5	jealous	2	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	5	conservative	1	egocentric	3	determined	4	moody	1

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-1,83	Openness/ Closedness	-2,67	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-2,50	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2,83	Resilience/ Neuroticism	0,00
sociable	2,83	curious	2,67	empathetic	2,83	flexible	3,17	balanced	2,50
enthusiastic	2,83	creative	2,50	cooperative	2,67	impulsive	2,67	optimistic	2,83
communicative	3,00	tolerant	3,00	friendly	2,83	carefree	2,33	resilient	2,83
reserved	3,33	suspicious	3,83	ambitious	3,50	organized	3,67	anxious	3,00
deliberate	3,17	formal	3,50	jealous	3,67	responsible	3,50	melancholic	2,33
independent	4,00	conservative	3,50	egocentric	3,67	determined	3,83	moody	2,83

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-2	Openness/ Closedness	-1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	0	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-1	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-1
sociable	2	curious	2	empathetic	3	flexible	3	balanced	4
enthusiastic	3	creative	4	cooperative	2	impulsive	3	optimistic	3
communicative	2	tolerant	4	friendly	2	carefree	4	resilient	3
reserved	2	suspicious	3	ambitious	3	organized	3	anxious	4
deliberate	3	formal	4	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	3
independent	4	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-0,07	Openness/ Closedness	0,79	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	0,93	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,69	Resilience/ Neuroticism	2,10
sociable	3,59	curious	3,62	empathetic	3,38	flexible	3,28	balanced	3,17
enthusiastic	3,14	creative	3,07	cooperative	3,28	impulsive	2,21	optimistic	3,59
communicative	3,59	tolerant	3,72	friendly	3,48	carefree	2,48	resilient	3,52
reserved	3,10	suspicious	3,41	ambitious	3,00	organized	3,83	anxious	3,07
deliberate	3,59	formal	2,48	jealous	2,72	responsible	4,07	melancholic	2,59
independent	3,69	conservative	3,72	egocentric	3,48	determined	3,76	moody	2,52

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1	Openness/ Closedness	4	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	5	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	1	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	5	flexible	4	balanced	3
enthusiastic	3	creative	4	cooperative	4	impulsive	3	optimistic	2
communicative	4	tolerant	4	friendly	3	carefree	4	resilient	5
reserved	3	suspicious	3	ambitious	3	organized	2	anxious	3
deliberate	3	formal	2	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	2
independent	4	conservative	3	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-0,48	Openness/ Closedness	-0,64	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2,92	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,88	Resilience/ Neuroticism	2,88
sociable	3,72	curious	3,44	empathetic	3,68	flexible	3,08	balanced	3,56
enthusiastic	3,32	creative	3,04	cooperative	3,52	impulsive	2,32	optimistic	3,60
communicative	3,20	tolerant	3,88	friendly	4,16	carefree	2,68	resilient	3,84
reserved	3,28	suspicious	3,24	ambitious	2,56	organized	4,04	anxious	3,04
deliberate	3,80	formal	3,64	jealous	2,96	responsible	4,16	melancholic	2,72
independent	3,64	conservative	4,12	egocentric	2,92	determined	3,76	moody	2,36

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-1	Openness/ Closedness	-4	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	5	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2	Resilience/ Neuroticism	5
sociable	4	curious	2	empathetic	4	flexible	5	balanced	4
enthusiastic	3	creative	4	cooperative	5	impulsive	4	optimistic	4
communicative	3	tolerant	2	friendly	5	carefree	4	resilient	4
reserved	3	suspicious	5	ambitious	3	organized	5	anxious	2
deliberate	4	formal	2	jealous	5	responsible	5	melancholic	3
independent	4	conservative	5	egocentric	1	determined	5	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1,71	Openness/ Closedness	1,00	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2,57	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-0,57	Resilience/ Neuroticism	2,43
sociable	4,14	curious	3,71	empathetic	4,00	flexible	4,29	balanced	3,29
enthusiastic	4,00	creative	3,14	cooperative	3,57	impulsive	3,71	optimistic	3,29
communicative	3,71	tolerant	3,57	friendly	3,43	carefree	2,86	resilient	3,29
reserved	3,43	suspicious	3,29	ambitious	2,71	organized	4,00	anxious	2,57
deliberate	2,86	formal	2,71	jealous	2,43	responsible	4,00	melancholic	2,00
independent	3,86	conservative	3,43	egocentric	3,29	determined	3,43	moody	2,86

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-.4	Openness/ Closedness	-.1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-.3	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-.4	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-.1
sociable	2	curious	3	empathetic	5	flexible	3	balanced	2
enthusiastic	3	creative	4	cooperative	2	impulsive	3	optimistic	3
communicative	4	tolerant	4	friendly	3	carefree	2	resilient	4
reserved	4	suspicious	5	ambitious	4	organized	4	anxious	3
deliberate	5	formal	3	jealous	5	responsible	4	melancholic	3
independent	4	conservative	4	egocentric	4	determined	4	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	0,93	Openness/ Closedness	1,57	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	0,36	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	0,21	Resilience/ Neuroticism	0,71
sociable	3,57	curious	3,50	empathetic	2,93	flexible	3,21	balanced	3,07
enthusiastic	3,50	creative	3,21	cooperative	3,50	impulsive	3,29	optimistic	3,43
communicative	2,93	tolerant	3,64	friendly	3,29	carefree	3,07	resilient	3,50
reserved	2,93	suspicious	2,64	ambitious	3,29	organized	3,07	anxious	2,93
deliberate	3,00	formal	2,71	jealous	2,79	responsible	3,43	melancholic	3,29
independent	3,14	conservative	3,43	egocentric	3,29	determined	2,86	moody	3,07

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1	Openness/ Closedness	-5	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	9	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	4	curious	2	empathetic	5	flexible	2	balanced	4
enthusiastic	4	creative	2	cooperative	4	impulsive	4	optimistic	3
communicative	3	tolerant	3	friendly	5	carefree	2	resilient	4
reserved	3	suspicious	3	ambitious	1	organized	4	anxious	4
deliberate	4	formal	4	jealous	2	responsible	3	melancholic	2
independent	3	conservative	5	egocentric	2	determined	3	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	2,64	Openness/ Closedness	2,45	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3,64	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	0,45	Resilience/ Neuroticism	4,73
sociable	4,09	curious	4,18	empathetic	3,64	flexible	3,64	balanced	3,73
enthusiastic	3,91	creative	4,00	cooperative	4,09	impulsive	3,64	optimistic	3,91
communicative	3,45	tolerant	3,91	friendly	3,82	carefree	3,91	resilient	3,91
reserved	2,55	suspicious	2,82	ambitious	2,91	organized	3,36	anxious	2,18
deliberate	3,27	formal	2,91	jealous	2,18	responsible	3,73	melancholic	2,36
independent	3,00	conservative	3,91	egocentric	2,82	determined	3,64	moody	2,27

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-2	Openness/ Closedness	2	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	4	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-2
sociable	3	curious	4	empathetic	5	flexible	4	balanced	3
enthusiastic	5	creative	4	cooperative	4	impulsive	3	optimistic	3
communicative	4	tolerant	4	friendly	5	carefree	1	resilient	4
reserved	5	suspicious	3	ambitious	3	organized	4	anxious	4
deliberate	4	formal	3	jealous	3	responsible	4	melancholic	4
independent	5	conservative	4	egocentric	4	determined	3	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	3,25	Openness/ Closedness	5,00	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3,42	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	3,21	Resilience/ Neuroticism	2,79
sociable	4,08	curious	4,21	empathetic	3,50	flexible	3,67	balanced	3,04
enthusiastic	4,00	creative	3,79	cooperative	3,79	impulsive	3,83	optimistic	3,83
communicative	3,00	tolerant	4,04	friendly	3,75	carefree	3,50	resilient	3,42
reserved	2,54	suspicious	2,46	ambitious	2,67	organized	2,50	anxious	2,46
deliberate	2,63	formal	1,96	jealous	2,42	responsible	2,67	melancholic	2,46
independent	2,67	conservative	2,63	egocentric	2,54	determined	2,63	moody	2,58

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-1	Openness/ Closedness	-5	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	8	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-10	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-3
sociable	4	curious	2	empathetic	4	flexible	1	balanced	3
enthusiastic	2	creative	2	cooperative	4	impulsive	2	optimistic	2
communicative	2	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	1	resilient	2
reserved	2	suspicious	4	ambitious	1	organized	5	anxious	5
deliberate	5	formal	5	jealous	3	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	2	conservative	5	egocentric	1	determined	4	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	4,54	Openness/ Closedness	3,13	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3,04	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	0,79	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,67
sociable	4,33	curious	4,13	empathetic	3,63	flexible	3,71	balanced	3,29
enthusiastic	4,17	creative	3,83	cooperative	3,79	impulsive	3,63	optimistic	3,92
communicative	3,75	tolerant	4,13	friendly	3,96	carefree	3,63	resilient	3,75
reserved	2,13	suspicious	2,88	ambitious	2,92	organized	3,33	anxious	2,42
deliberate	2,67	formal	2,75	jealous	2,46	responsible	3,58	melancholic	2,25
independent	2,92	conservative	3,33	egocentric	2,96	determined	3,25	moody	2,63

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-4	Openness/ Closedness	-1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	1	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-2
sociable	4	curious	3	empathetic	4	flexible	4	balanced	2
enthusiastic	2	creative	3	cooperative	3	impulsive	1	optimistic	3
communicative	2	tolerant	4	friendly	4	carefree	1	resilient	3
reserved	4	suspicious	5	ambitious	4	organized	2	anxious	5
deliberate	5	formal	2	jealous	4	responsible	4	melancholic	2
independent	3	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	2	moody	3

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-2,59	Openness/ Closedness	-2,78	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-0,26	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,52	Resilience/ Neuroticism	0,07
sociable	2,89	curious	2,59	empathetic	2,96	flexible	2,67	balanced	3,11
enthusiastic	2,67	creative	2,59	cooperative	2,70	impulsive	2,26	optimistic	2,78
communicative	3,04	tolerant	3,26	friendly	3,48	carefree	2,81	resilient	3,30
reserved	3,48	suspicious	3,48	ambitious	3,07	organized	3,85	anxious	3,07
deliberate	3,74	formal	3,52	jealous	3,04	responsible	3,93	melancholic	3,00
independent	3,96	conservative	4,22	egocentric	3,30	determined	3,48	moody	3,04

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	2	Openness/ Closedness	0	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	1	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-1	Resilience/ Neuroticism	1
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	2	flexible	3	balanced	2
enthusiastic	3	creative	4	cooperative	3	impulsive	4	optimistic	3
communicative	3	tolerant	3	friendly	3	carefree	2	resilient	2
reserved	3	suspicious	4	ambitious	3	organized	2	anxious	2
deliberate	1	formal	3	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	2
independent	4	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion bis Introversion	2,80	Openness/ Closedness	0,80	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	1,60	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	2,20	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,60
gesellig	4,20	curious	3,60	empathetic	3,70	flexible	3,70	balanced	3,40
enthusiastisch	4,00	creative	3,00	cooperative	3,90	impulsive	3,30	optimistic	3,90
kommunikativ	4,00	tolerant	3,30	friendly	4,00	carefree	3,60	resilient	3,80
zurückhaltend	2,90	suspicious	3,30	ambitious	3,20	organized	2,60	anxious	2,50
bedächtig	2,80	formal	2,80	jealous	3,30	responsible	2,70	melancholic	2,40
unabhängig	3,70	conservative	3,00	egocentric	3,50	determined	3,10	moody	2,60

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	5	Openness/ Closedness	2	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	6	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	0	Resilience/ Neuroticism	8
sociable	5	curious	5	empathetic	4	flexible	5	balanced	3
enthusiastic	5	creative	3	cooperative	5	impulsive	5	optimistic	5
communicative	5	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	5	resilient	5
reserved	2	suspicious	4	ambitious	3	organized	5	anxious	2
deliberate	4	formal	2	jealous	3	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	4	conservative	5	egocentric	2	determined	5	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	6,27	Openness/ Closedness	5,27	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3,45	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	0,73	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,00
sociable	4,64	curious	4,55	empathetic	4,09	flexible	3,73	balanced	2,73
enthusiastic	4,36	creative	3,73	cooperative	3,73	impulsive	3,45	optimistic	4,09
communicative	4,36	tolerant	4,18	friendly	4,27	carefree	3,45	resilient	3,73
reserved	1,73	suspicious	2,45	ambitious	2,55	organized	3,27	anxious	2,36
deliberate	2,82	formal	1,82	jealous	3,27	responsible	3,27	melancholic	2,27
independent	2,55	conservative	2,91	egocentric	2,82	determined	3,36	moody	2,91

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1	Offenheit/Verschlossenheit	-7	Verträglichkeit/Unverträglichkeit	0	Spontanität/Gewissenhaftigkeit	-7	Resilienz/Neurotizismus	8
sociable	5	neugierig	3	empathisch	3	flexibel	4	ausgeglichen	3
enthusiastic	2	kreativ	2	kooperativ	3	impulsiv	2	optimistisch	4
communicative	5	tolerant	2	freundlich	4	sorglos	2	belastbar	5
reserved	2	misstrauisch	5	ehrgeizig	4	organisiert	5	ängstlich	2
deliberate	5	formell	4	eifersüchtig	2	verantwortungsvoll	5	melancholisch	1
independent	4	konservativ	5	egozentrisch	4	zielstrebig	5	launisch	1

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	0,50	Offenheit bis Verschlossenheit	2,20	Verträglichkeit bis Unverträglichkeit	2,10	Spontanität bis Gewissenhaftigkeit	-2,40	Resilienz bis Neurotizismus	0,80
sociable	3,70	neugierig	4,00	empathisch	3,70	flexibel	2,90	ausgeglichen	2,80
enthusiastic	3,30	kreativ	3,80	kooperativ	3,10	impulsiv	2,40	optimistisch	3,70
communicative	4,20	tolerant	3,70	freundlich	4,30	sorglos	2,70	belastbar	3,70
reserved	3,00	misstrauisch	3,60	ehrgeizig	2,50	organisiert	3,50	ängstlich	2,90
deliberate	3,70	formell	2,30	eifersüchtig	3,50	verantwortungsvoll	3,50	melancholisch	3,20
independent	4,00	konservativ	3,40	egozentrisch	3,00	zielstrebig	3,40	launisch	3,30

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-4	Openness/ Closedness	3	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	0	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-8	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-2
sociable	2	curious	4	empathetic	3	flexible	1	balanced	4
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	2	impulsive	1	optimistic	3
communicative	3	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	2	resilient	3
reserved	5	suspicious	3	ambitious	3	organized	4	anxious	4
deliberate	3	formal	2	jealous	4	responsible	4	melancholic	4
independent	5	conservative	4	egocentric	3	determined	4	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-3,60	Openness/ Closedness	-3,84	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-0,92	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,24	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-1,00
sociable	2,76	curious	2,04	empathetic	3,08	flexible	2,72	balanced	3,16
enthusiastic	2,68	creative	2,08	cooperative	2,56	impulsive	2,32	optimistic	2,68
communicative	3,04	tolerant	3,12	friendly	3,36	carefree	2,56	resilient	2,92
reserved	4,00	suspicious	3,24	ambitious	2,88	organized	3,92	anxious	3,56
deliberate	4,00	formal	3,76	jealous	3,68	responsible	3,76	melancholic	3,16
independent	4,08	conservative	4,08	egocentric	3,36	determined	3,16	moody	3,04

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	2	Openness/ Closedness	0	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	4	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-7	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	4	curious	4	empathetic	3	flexible	3	balanced	1
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	5	impulsive	4	optimistic	4
communicative	4	tolerant	3	friendly	4	carefree	1	resilient	4
reserved	3	suspicious	5	ambitious	1	organized	5	anxious	3
deliberate	4	formal	1	jealous	4	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	3	conservative	4	egocentric	3	determined	5	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	4,50	Openness/ Closedness	4,86	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	1,93	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	1,36	Resilience/ Neuroticism	0,64
sociable	4,00	curious	4,00	empathetic	3,79	flexible	3,57	balanced	2,93
enthusiastic	4,07	creative	3,64	cooperative	3,43	impulsive	3,86	optimistic	3,64
communicative	4,07	tolerant	4,07	friendly	3,93	carefree	3,86	resilient	3,36
reserved	2,07	suspicious	2,29	ambitious	2,79	organized	2,93	anxious	2,93
deliberate	2,64	formal	2,00	jealous	3,21	responsible	3,71	melancholic	2,79
independent	2,93	conservative	2,57	egocentric	3,21	determined	3,29	moody	3,57

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	4	Openness/ Closedness	3	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	3	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-6	Resilience/ Neuroticism	6
sociable	4	curious	5	empathetic	2	flexible	4	balanced	4
enthusiastic	5	creative	3	cooperative	4	impulsive	2	optimistic	3
communicative	4	tolerant	3	friendly	2	carefree	2	resilient	4
reserved	1	suspicious	3	ambitious	1	organized	5	anxious	2
deliberate	4	formal	1	jealous	2	responsible	5	melancholic	1
independent	4	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	4	moody	2

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-5,70	Openness/ Closedness	-2,80	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-1,70	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2,80	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-1,50
sociable	2,10	curious	2,50	empathetic	2,50	flexible	2,80	balanced	3,30
enthusiastic	2,10	creative	2,50	cooperative	2,10	impulsive	2,40	optimistic	2,20
communicative	2,20	tolerant	3,60	friendly	2,90	carefree	2,60	resilient	3,10
reserved	3,70	suspicious	3,80	ambitious	2,80	organized	3,40	anxious	3,80
deliberate	3,90	formal	4,20	jealous	3,30	responsible	3,60	melancholic	3,30
independent	4,50	conservative	3,40	egocentric	3,10	determined	3,60	moody	3,00

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-1	Openness/ Closedness	1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-4	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3	Resilience/ Neuroticism	5
sociable	3	curious	5	empathetic	2	flexible	5	balanced	4
enthusiastic	2	creative	4	cooperative	3	impulsive	2	optimistic	1
communicative	3	tolerant	2	friendly	1	carefree	2	resilient	4
reserved	1	suspicious	4	ambitious	3	organized	3	anxious	2
deliberate	5	formal	4	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	1
independent	3	conservative	2	egocentric	5	determined	5	moody	1

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-3,33	Openness/ Closedness	-2,13	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-0,47	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3,80	Resilience/ Neuroticism	1,93
sociable	2,67	curious	2,93	empathetic	3,07	flexible	2,67	balanced	3,67
enthusiastic	2,73	creative	2,60	cooperative	2,47	impulsive	2,53	optimistic	2,93
communicative	2,93	tolerant	3,00	friendly	3,27	carefree	2,60	resilient	3,47
reserved	3,47	suspicious	3,60	ambitious	3,07	organized	3,87	anxious	2,87
deliberate	3,93	formal	3,67	jealous	2,53	responsible	3,93	melancholic	2,80
independent	4,27	conservative	3,40	egocentric	3,67	determined	3,80	moody	2,47

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1	Openness/ Closedness	5	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	6	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-3	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-5
sociable	4	curious	2	empathetic	4	flexible	2	balanced	1
enthusiastic	3	creative	5	cooperative	5	impulsive	3	optimistic	1
communicative	4	tolerant	4	friendly	5	carefree	2	resilient	2
reserved	2	suspicious	4	ambitious	3	organized	4	anxious	3
deliberate	3	formal	1	jealous	3	responsible	4	melancholic	3
independent	5	conservative	1	egocentric	2	determined	2	moody	3

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-0,75	Openness/ Closedness	-2,25	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-2,25	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-0,75	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-0,75
sociable	2,75	curious	2,50	empathetic	2,75	flexible	2,50	balanced	2,75
enthusiastic	3,00	creative	3,00	cooperative	2,50	impulsive	3,00	optimistic	2,50
communicative	3,25	tolerant	3,25	friendly	2,75	carefree	3,00	resilient	2,50
reserved	3,50	suspicious	3,50	ambitious	3,25	organized	3,25	anxious	2,75
deliberate	3,00	formal	3,75	jealous	3,25	responsible	3,00	melancholic	3,25
independent	3,25	conservative	3,75	egocentric	3,75	determined	3,00	moody	2,50

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-2	Openness/ Closedness	1	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	7	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-6	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-8
sociable	5	curious	4	empathetic	5	flexible	1	balanced	2
enthusiastic	4	creative	5	cooperative	4	impulsive	1	optimistic	2
communicative	2	tolerant	5	friendly	5	carefree	1	resilient	2
reserved	4	suspicious	5	ambitious	3	organized	3	anxious	5
deliberate	5	formal	3	jealous	2	responsible	4	melancholic	4
independent	4	conservative	5	egocentric	2	determined	2	moody	5

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	3,25	Openness/ Closedness	2,58	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	2,08	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	2,50	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3,00
sociable	4,00	curious	3,92	empathetic	3,42	flexible	3,58	balanced	3,08
enthusiastic	4,08	creative	3,58	cooperative	4,08	impulsive	4,00	optimistic	3,92
communicative	3,50	tolerant	3,67	friendly	3,33	carefree	4,00	resilient	3,67
reserved	2,42	suspicious	3,00	ambitious	2,92	organized	2,58	anxious	2,25
deliberate	2,92	formal	2,25	jealous	2,42	responsible	3,17	melancholic	2,67
independent	3,00	conservative	3,33	egocentric	3,42	determined	3,33	moody	2,75

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-1	Openness/ Closedness	3	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	-2	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	3	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-2
sociable	3	curious	2	empathetic	4	flexible	4	balanced	3
enthusiastic	2	creative	4	cooperative	4	impulsive	3	optimistic	2
communicative	4	tolerant	5	friendly	2	carefree	2	resilient	3
reserved	4	suspicious	4	ambitious	3	organized	2	anxious	4
deliberate	2	formal	2	jealous	4	responsible	2	melancholic	2
independent	4	conservative	2	egocentric	5	determined	2	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	-2,12	Openness/ Closedness	-1,42	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	0,04	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	-2,04	Resilience/ Neuroticism	-0,19
sociable	3,08	curious	2,69	empathetic	3,27	flexible	2,81	balanced	3,04
enthusiastic	2,81	creative	3,00	cooperative	2,92	impulsive	2,69	optimistic	2,92
communicative	3,00	tolerant	3,65	friendly	3,65	carefree	2,73	resilient	3,04
reserved	3,50	suspicious	3,65	ambitious	3,15	organized	3,54	anxious	3,19
deliberate	3,77	formal	3,42	jealous	3,27	responsible	3,46	melancholic	3,19
independent	3,73	conservative	3,69	egocentric	3,38	determined	3,27	moody	2,81

Selbstwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	1	Openness/ Closedness	4	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	5	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	7	Resilience/ Neuroticism	3
sociable	5	curious	5	empathetic	4	flexible	5	balanced	4
enthusiastic	4	creative	3	cooperative	5	impulsive	4	optimistic	3
communicative	4	tolerant	4	friendly	3	carefree	4	resilient	3
reserved	4	suspicious	3	ambitious	4	organized	2	anxious	1
deliberate	5	formal	1	jealous	1	responsible	3	melancholic	2
independent	3	conservative	4	egocentric	2	determined	1	moody	4

Fremdwahrnehmung

Extraversion/ Introversion	4,60	Openness/ Closedness	5,53	Agreeableness/ Disagreeableness	4,40	Spontaneity/ Conscientiousness	2,27	Resilience/ Neuroticism	4,67
sociable	4,47	curious	4,60	empathetic	3,67	flexible	3,73	balanced	3,40
enthusiastic	4,20	creative	4,40	cooperative	4,33	impulsive	4,20	optimistic	4,13
communicative	3,33	tolerant	4,13	friendly	4,07	carefree	3,80	resilient	3,93
reserved	2,33	suspicious	2,73	ambitious	2,40	organized	2,73	anxious	2,27
deliberate	2,53	formal	1,93	jealous	2,20	responsible	3,33	melancholic	2,20
independent	2,53	conservative	2,93	egocentric	3,07	determined	3,40	moody	2,33

Appendix C: Modified Big Five Model

Objective and Methodology

This experiment was conducted to investigate the isolated influence of color choice on personality perception in the modified Big Five test. A clothing circle with high vibrancy, previously rated as highly extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient in a prior survey, was manipulated in color using an image editing program to create three variants (A, B, C). The shape, arrangement, and structure of the clothing circle remained unchanged to exclude other influencing factors. The participants (approximately 20 per evaluation) were unaware that they were re-evaluating the same clothing circle with altered color schemes, as the assessments took place at different times. Evaluations were conducted anonymously and solely based on the color circle, without information about the person, clothing style, brand, or previous ratings.

A second experiment was conducted following the same methodology but using a different original color circle. This second original color circle consisted of approximately 50% white, with the remaining colors in descending order of proportion: beige, brown, black, red, pink, orange, and yellow. The Big Five traits for this circle were rated in the mid-range, with a tendency toward higher Agreeableness and Resilience. Two additional variants (A and B) were created for this second experiment, manipulating the color composition while keeping the clothing structure unchanged.

Color Variants First Experiment

- **Original:** High vibrancy with diverse, vivid colors, rated as highly extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient.
- **Variant A:** Reduced vibrancy with a dominance of red tones, which may evoke associations such as passion or dominance (Elliot & Maier, 2014).
- **Variant B:** Reduced vibrancy with a dominance of yellow tones, potentially associated with optimism or friendliness (Maier et al., 2009).
- **Variant C:** Strongly reduced vibrancy with a dominance of khaki brown tones, perceived as sober or conservative (Whitfield & Wiltshire, 1990).

Color Variants Second Experiment

- **Original:** Approximately 50% white, with remaining colors in descending order: beige, brown, black, red, pink, orange, and yellow. Rated in the mid-range for Big Five traits, with a tendency toward higher Agreeableness and Resilience.
- **Variant A:** Exclusively white clothing, leading to a significant shift in ratings across all five personality dimensions. The person was rated as maximally introverted, closed, slightly disagreeable, and maximally conscientious, with a shift in the Resilience–Neuroticism dimension from resilient to slightly neurotic.
- **Variant B:** Predominantly recolored with warm tones (orange, apricot, sand, ochre, and yellow), with only about 20% white remaining. This led to a shift in ratings across all dimensions toward higher Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Spontaneity, and Resilience.

Results First Experiment

The experiment confirmed the influence of color choice on personality perception. Ratings shifted in all variants compared to the original, with Variant C showing the most extreme shift:

- **Variant C (Brown tones):** Ratings reversed to the opposite poles in all dimensions. The person was rated as highly introverted, closed, disagreeable, and conscientious. In the Resilience–Neuroticism dimension, the rating was neutral (“both”).

- **Variant B (Yellow tones):** Slight shift toward the opposite poles (Introversion, Closedness, Disagreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism), but less pronounced than in Variant C.
- **Variant A (Red tones):** Minimal shift toward the opposite poles, with slight tendencies toward Introversion, Closedness, Disagreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Neuroticism.

Results Second Experiment

The second experiment further validated the influence of color manipulation on personality perception:

- **Variant A (Exclusively white):** The exclusive use of white clothing resulted in a significant shift in ratings across all five personality dimensions. The person was perceived as maximally introverted, closed, slightly disagreeable, and maximally conscientious, with a shift in the Resilience–Neuroticism dimension from resilient to slightly neurotic.
- **Variant B (Warm tones):** The dominance of warm colors (orange, apricot, sand, ochre, yellow) with only 20% white remaining led to a marked shift toward higher Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Spontaneity, and Resilience, demonstrating the strong impact of warmer colors on perceived personality traits.

Interpretation

The results of both experiments underscore the validity of the color psychology method, as color manipulation, while keeping the clothing structure unchanged, elicited significant changes in other-perception. In the first experiment, the extreme shift in Variant C demonstrates that sober, less vibrant colors (brown tones) are associated with conservative, introverted, and conscientious personality traits, while vivid colors (Original) signal Extraversion and Openness (Elliot & Maier, 2014). The less pronounced shifts in Variants A and B suggest that red and yellow tones evoke weaker connotations but still influence perception.

In the second experiment, the exclusive use of white in Variant A led to perceptions of introversion, closedness, and slight disagreeableness, likely due to the sterile or reserved connotations of white. Conversely, the warm tones in Variant B fostered perceptions of Extraversion, Openness, and Resilience, aligning with associations of warmth and friendliness (Maier et al., 2009). These findings confirm that color preferences, independent of other factors, are a robust indicator of perceived personality traits and can reveal dissonances in personality perception. The experiments collectively highlight the nuanced interplay between color and personality perception, supporting the metaphor of the “wardrobe as a diary” (Hebdige, 1979).

First Manipulation of the colors of a clothing circle

Second Manipulation of the colors of a clothing circle

Original

Version A

Version B

Appendix D: Extreme Ratings in the Five Personality Dimensions

This appendix describes the most extreme ratings in the five dimensions of the Big Five personality test (Extraversion–Introversion, Openness–Closedness, Agreeableness–Disagreeableness, Spontaneity–Conscientiousness, Resilience–Neuroticism) based on the color characteristics of clothing circles. The color features of the clothing circles serve as indicators of the personality traits of the examined individuals.

High Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Spontaneity, and Resilience

Clothing circles associated with high scores in Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, Spontaneity, and Resilience exhibit exclusively high vibrancy. This ranges from light, pastel colors to highly saturated, diverse colors.

- **Extraversion, Openness, Spontaneity, and Resilience:** The top rankings are occupied by clothing circles with the highest vibrancy, saturation, color contrasts, and diversity. This reflects a lively, creative, and resilient personality.
- **Agreeableness:** The top ranking is held by a clothing circle with predominantly pastel colors and high vibrancy, indicating a friendly and harmony-oriented personality.

High Introversion, Closedness, Disagreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Neuroticism

Clothing circles associated with high scores in Introversion, Closedness, Disagreeableness, Conscientiousness, and Neuroticism are exclusively white, gray, black, or dominated by brown and blue tones.

- **Introversion, Closedness, and Conscientiousness:** The top ranking is held by a purely white clothing circle, indicating a reserved, structured, and dutiful personality.
- **Disagreeableness and Neuroticism:** Nearly black clothing circles occupy the top ranking, suggesting a conflict-prone and emotionally unstable personality.

Conclusion

The analysis demonstrates that the color characteristics of clothing circles are a clear indicator of personality traits. High vibrancy correlates with open, spontaneous, and resilient personalities, while monochrome and dark colors indicate introverted, conscientious, or neurotic traits.

Extraverted

53/ 6,64

245009/ 6,27

06/ 5,11

75/ 4,64

07/ 4,6

Openness

06/ 5,61

07/ 5,53

53/ 5,5

245009/ 5,27

22/ 5,22

Agreeable

80/ 4,93

81/ 4,75

53/ 4,61

20/ 4,56

07/ 4,4

Spontaneity

53/ 3,71

22/ 3,35

06/ 2,96

09/ 2,5

07/ 2,27

Resilience

53/ 5,36

27/ 4,73

07/ 4,47

06/ 4,44

13/4
54/69

Introverted

69/ -5,06

56/ -5,57

54/ -5,65

245011/ -5,7

66/ -6,24

Closedness

56/ -4

28/ -4,04

245008/ -4,5

69/ -5,65

66/ -5,65

Disagreeable

56/ -2,21

51/ -2,46

63/ -2,61

54/ -3,54

69/ -4,29

Conscientiousness

245008/ -4,83

63/ -5,09

65/ -5,41

69/ -5,47

66/ -6,71

Neuroticism

51/ -1,36

245011/ -1,5

63/ -1,69

69/ -1,88

54/ -2

55/69

Appendix E: Interviews with Participants Showing Significant Differences in Self- and Other-Assessment

Introduction

The following interview transcripts contain the statements of three female participants for whom significant differences were identified between self-assessment and external assessment in the personality dimensions. The interviews were conducted as part of a study on color psychology and its influence on the perception of personality. Each interview has been anonymized and assigned a unique participant ID, enabling a link to the color circles presented in the study.

In addition, the participants were asked to provide a second self-assessment as well as an assessment from a close acquaintance, in order to create a basis for comparison. The transcripts have been linguistically smoothed to ensure clear and precise presentation, with irrelevant passages marked and omitted. Each transcript section is accompanied by a brief summary highlighting the relevant statements.

Furthermore, illustrations of all 29 color circles and the evaluation of the corresponding self- and external assessments are included as an appendix. The external assessment by the seminar group is based solely on the quantitative and qualitative composition of the clothing colors in the color circle, without any further information about the participants, such as physical appearance or personal characteristics.

Interview with Participant 23450003 (Color Circle)

Summary:

The 24-year-old participant describes herself as introverted, creative, and structured, with preferences for quiet activities such as cooking, painting, and maintaining her aquarium. In everyday life, she favors comfortable, neutral clothing (black, white, gray), but for special occasions, she wears striking, shiny outfits to attract attention. This stylistic variability reflects her mood-dependent self-perception, fluctuating between introversion and extraversion. The seminar group, analyzing only the color circle, perceived her as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient, likely due to the halo effect triggered by the vibrant, colorful clothing items in the color circle. Her second self-assessment shows alignment with the other-assessment in the Agreeableness dimension, suggesting unstable self-esteem. The participant emphasizes her independence, perfectionism, and authenticity but acknowledges weaknesses such as impatience and holding grudges. Her frequently changing hair colors, tattoos, and piercings, unknown to the seminar group, underscore personality dissonances that may influence the variability of her self-assessment.

Psychological Analysis of Discrepancies Between Self- and Other-Perception:

The experimental setting, where the seminar group conducted the Big Five personality test based solely on the quantitative and qualitative composition of clothing colors in the color circle (Fig. 1), without additional information about the participant, shapes the analysis of discrepancies between self- and other-perception. The participant describes herself as introverted, conscientious, and neurotic (“I am impatient, jealous in relationships, stubborn, and hold grudges” [#00:15:56]), while the seminar group assessed her as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient. This discrepancy can be explained depth-psychologically through a combination of projective bias, halo effect, and internal dissonances in the participant’s personality.

Projective Bias and Halo Effect Through the Color Circle:

The seminar group had no information about the participant except the color circle, which included both neutral (black, white, gray) and striking, saturated colors (red, pink, shiny fabrics). The participant confirms: “People thought I was more open because of the colorful clothes” [#00:25:47]. Depth-psychologically, this indicates a projective bias, where the seminar group interpreted the vibrant, shiny clothing as indicators of extraversion and openness. The halo effect amplified this perception, as striking colors are unconsciously associated with an extraverted, confident personality. However, the participant wears these items contextually: “For special occasions, I wear sparkling, colorful clothing, but only in close circles” [#00:10:28]. Since the seminar group was unaware of this context, their isolated evaluation of the color circle led to a distorted assessment, overlooking her everyday neutral, comfortable clothing.

Internal Dissonances and Ambivalent Self-Concept:

The participant’s self-perception as introverted and conscientious contrasts with her situational extraversion, which she acknowledges: “I’m either completely introverted or completely extraverted on a given day, depending on my mood” [#00:26:44]. This mood-dependent variability suggests an ambivalent self-concept, which, depth-psychologically, may stem from unconscious conflicts between a desire for withdrawal (“My safe space is video games” [#00:03:56]) and a need for self-expression and social recognition (“For photoshoots, I wear extravagant outfits that I post on social media” [#00:29:59]). Her statement, “You should stay authentic everywhere in life” [#00:19:29], contradicts her practice of deliberately choosing striking outfits for social recognition, suggesting unconscious adaptation to external expectations. This dissonance is reinforced by her second self-assessment, which aligns with the other-perception in Agreeableness, indicating unstable self-esteem (“The second self-assessment might relate to a better mood”).

Role of Non-Visible Characteristics (Hair Colors, Tattoos, Piercings):

Although the seminar group was unaware of the participant’s frequently changing hair colors, tattoos, and piercings, these characteristics underscore the internal dissonances in her personality. She describes: “I often dye my hair, from red to blonde, and wear many visible tattoos and piercings. I like experimenting with my appearance” [#00:28:02]. This tendency toward impulsive, striking changes in appearance contrasts with her self-description as introverted and structured (“I like to plan ahead” [#00:21:20]). Depth-psychologically, this could be interpreted as an unconscious attempt to compensate for internal insecurities or conflicts through external self-expression. Her statement, “My neutral facial expression is often misunderstood as negative” [#00:25:47], suggests awareness of the discrepancy between her internal experience and external perception, potentially amplifying her neurotic tendencies (impatience, jealousy, holding grudges [#00:15:56]). These characteristics, though invisible to the seminar group, reflect a personality oscillating between control and impulsivity, explaining the variability in her self-assessment.

Summary of Psychological Causes:

The discrepancies between self- and other-perception result from a combination of external and internal factors. The seminar group projected an extraverted, open personality based on the vibrant colors in the color circle, amplified by the halo effect, without knowing the contextual use of this clothing. Meanwhile, the participant exhibits an ambivalent self-concept, shaped by unconscious conflicts between introversion and a desire for social recognition. Her stylistic variability (neutral everyday clothing vs. extravagant event outfits) and impulsive changes in appearance (hair colors, tattoos) reflect these dissonances, explaining her unstable self-assessment. The other-perception overestimates her extraversion, as it does not account for the introverted aspects of her personality that dominate in everyday life.

Transcript:

B: Participant, I: Interviewer

I: Thank you for taking the time. I’m writing my bachelor’s thesis on the color psychology seminar and the

corresponding color circles. The interview will be anonymously transcribed. Could you first tell me about yourself? How old are you, and what are your hobbies?

B: I'm 24 years old. In my free time, I like staying at home, meeting friends for relaxed evenings, or cooking something delicious. I paint, take photos, bake, and play video games, which are a safe space for me. I also maintain a 30-liter aquarium with guppies and shrimp. I avoid large crowds, but concerts are an exception. [...]

I: Can you describe your color circle? What's your favorite clothing item?

B: My favorite clothing items are jackets, like leather or faux fur jackets, that complete my outfit. They're not in the color circle since I only included clothes from my wardrobe. [...] When sorting, I found old red and pink pajamas that I've already discarded because they no longer fit.

I: What clothing do you wear when you want to feel comfortable?

B: At home, I wear comfortable, oversized clothing like sweatpants or pajamas, which I wouldn't wear in public. When out, I ensure my clothing is comfortable but presentable.

I: Do you shop based on trends or your taste?

B: I follow trends if I like them. For special occasions, like birthdays or photoshoots, I wear extravagant, shiny clothing to attract attention, like a sequined dress or a green two-piece. I often wear these once and sell them afterward. [...]

I: Can your color circle be divided into everyday and extravagant clothing?

B: Yes, in everyday life, I wear neutral colors like black, white, or gray. At home, I wear cozy, colorful pajamas, and for special occasions, I wear sparkling, vibrant clothing, but only in close circles.

I: How would people who know you well describe you in three words?

B: Humorous, headstrong, and unstoppable. I have an ironic sense of humor, I'm ambitious, and I don't let things stop me, as shown by my many tattoos, which I got despite my mother's objections. I'm headstrong because I defend my opinions, even if I listen to others.

I: What's particularly important to you in life?

B: My mother is my role model and the most important person in my life. Physical and mental health, as well as my car, a Hyundai E10, are also very important. [...]

I: What weaknesses would you like to work on?

B: I'm impatient, jealous in relationships, stubborn, and hold grudges. I return good tenfold and bad fiftyfold.

I: What strengths have helped you in life?

B: My ability to be alone is my greatest strength. It's important to know yourself and be independent without needing constant social contact.

I: Do you compare yourself to others?

B: No, comparing myself to others is unhealthy. I'm my own competition and focus on myself.

I: Is it important to you to be authentic?

B: Yes, authenticity is essential. I don't pretend to please others. Either people like me, or they don't—it doesn't matter to me.

I: Is it hard for you to consider tasks complete?

B: I work until the deadline, but then I make sure everything is perfect. I don't do things halfway, in life in

general. [...]

I: Would you spontaneously travel to Italy with a friend?

B: No, that's too spontaneous for me. I like to plan ahead, especially for travel. Spontaneous meetups, like going to McDonald's, are fine, though.

I: How did you perceive the personality test in the seminar?

B: The test was fun because I enjoy self-assessments. The questions and response options were good, neither too long nor too short, and I could answer in a nuanced way.

I: Your self-assessment differs significantly from the seminar group's other-perception, which rated you as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient. Why might that be?

B: The seminar group doesn't really know me and probably thought I was more open and extraverted because of the colorful clothing in the color circle. My neutral facial expression is often misunderstood as negative, even though I'm different inside. I can be very introverted or extraverted depending on my mood, which my clothing reflects.

I: Was there anything in the evaluation that surprised you?

B: No, I understand the assessment. I can be very extraverted depending on the setting and occasion. My outfits, especially the glittery ones, reflect that.

I: Anything else you'd like to add?

B: I often dye my hair, from red to blonde, and wear many visible tattoos and piercings. I like experimenting with my appearance, sometimes with wigs, especially for photoshoots with friends that I post on social media. My hair colors and outfits depend on my mood. [...]

Interview with Participant 23450009 (Color Circle)

Summary:

The 27-year-old participant describes herself as creative, communicative, empathetic, but also neurotic, self-critical, and plan-oriented. Her clothing, representing only a quarter of her wardrobe (fall clothing), is seasonal and varied, ranging from pastel colors in spring to dark, gothic-punk tones in winter. She emphasizes that the restriction to fall clothing distorted the overall impression, as her inner state fluctuates significantly between seasons, reflected in her clothing ("I dress entirely according to my mood" [#01:12:35]). Her "cartoon outfit" (jeans, flannel shirts, Chucks) symbolizes consistency, while her Russian heritage shapes her "color homeland," potentially distorting the other-perception. The seminar group, seeing only the color circle, uniformly rated her positively as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient, while she perceives herself as introverted and neurotic. Her second self-assessment shows a shift toward extraversion but remains otherwise stable. An assessment by a close acquaintance lies between her two self-assessments in extraversion but confirms the neuroticism discrepancy. Her passion for costume-making (cosplay, historical clothing) and body dysmorphia suggest an ambivalent identity oscillating between self-expression and adaptation.

Psychological Analysis of Discrepancies Between Self- and Other-Perception:

The experimental setting, in which the seminar group conducted the Big Five personality test based solely on the quantitative and qualitative composition of fall clothing in the color circle (Fig. 2), without further information about the participant, shapes the analysis of discrepancies between self- and other-perception.

The participant describes herself as introverted, neurotic, and conscientious (“I’m very plan-oriented, serious, calculative” [#00:38:16]), while the seminar group assessed her as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient. This discrepancy can be explained depth-psychologically through projective biases, the halo effect, distortion due to the restriction to fall clothing, and internal dissonances in the participant’s personality, amplified by her seasonally fluctuating clothing choices and cultural background.

Projective Bias and Halo Effect Through the Restricted Color Circle:

The seminar group had access only to the color circle, which depicted the participant’s fall clothing, consisting of warm, autumnal tones (brown, dark green, burgundy) and checkered flannel shirts, excluding her bright summer colors, pastel spring colors, or dark, gothic-punk winter outfits. The participant emphasizes: “The color circle is a quarter of my tops, seasonally selected” [#00:11:58]. This restriction to fall clothing distorted the overall impression, as her clothing choice strongly depends on her seasonally fluctuating inner state: “I dress entirely according to my mood” [#01:12:35]. The seminar group likely interpreted the variety and warm, autumnal colors as expressions of openness, vitality, and stability, amplified by the halo effect. Depth-psychologically, this suggests a projective bias, where the seminar group associated the colors and patterns (e.g., checkered shirts) with an extraverted, positive personality, without knowing the contextual and mood-dependent use of the clothing. The absence of neon colors, gothic elements, or festive clothing in the color circle led to a homogeneous, positive assessment that failed to capture the complexity of her personality and the seasonal fluctuations in her inner state. The participant confirms: “My clothing doesn’t always represent my mental state” [#01:13:06], amplifying the discrepancy, as the seminar group saw only a segment of her wardrobe that did not reflect her neurotic or introverted phases, which manifest in other seasons (e.g., winter with gothic-punk outfits).

Internal Dissonances and Ambivalent Self-Concept:

The participant exhibits an ambivalent self-concept, oscillating between creative-chaotic and structured-plan-oriented poles: “I’m artistically chaotic but also serious, plan-oriented, calculative” [#00:38:18]. This duality is reflected in her clothing choices, ranging from neon to gothic-punk, but also in her “cartoon outfit” (jeans, flannel shirts, Chucks), which symbolizes consistency and pragmatism [#00:24:18]. The seasonal variability of her clothing—pastel in spring, bright in summer, warm in fall, dark and gothic in winter—mirrors her strongly fluctuating inner state, shaped by ADHD (“My thoughts are like a ball of yarn” [#00:43:05]) and body dysmorphia (“I rarely wear form-fitting clothing” [#00:33:41]). Depth-psychologically, this suggests unconscious conflicts between a desire for self-expression and a need for stability and comfort, developed in response to unstable life phases: “Stability is important to me because I rarely had it” [#00:41:57]. Her self-perception as neurotic (“I often worry, lose motivation quickly” [#01:09:14]) contrasts with the other-perception as resilient, indicating a discrepancy between internal experience and external presentation. The restriction to fall clothing in the color circle amplified this discrepancy, as the seminar group did not see the dark, winter outfits (which could reflect her neurotic side) or the bright summer outfits (showing her creative, vibrant side), only the autumnal colors suggesting stability and balance.

Cultural Background and “Color Homeland”:

The participant’s Russian heritage shapes her “color homeland,” which the seminar group may not have grasped: “My Russian background might have caused a misjudgment” [#01:12:35]. In Russian culture, colors like red carry strong emotional significance, which she associates with her neurotic side (“I have a lot of red, which might point to my neurotic side”). The seminar group, unaware of this cultural connotation, interpreted the autumnal colors more neutrally and positively, amplifying the distortion caused by the restricted clothing selection. Depth-psychologically, this suggests an unconscious projection of her cultural identity through clothing, while the seminar group perceived it as universally positive. Her passion for costume-making (cosplay, historical clothing) [#00:54:15] underscores her inclination toward role diversity, weakening her identity consistency and reinforcing the other-perception as spontaneous, though she describes herself as plan-oriented (“I’m very calculative” [#00:38:18]). The restriction to fall clothing

prevented the seminar group from recognizing this role diversity, as the extreme expressions (neon in summer, gothic in winter) were absent, which would have better represented her neurotic and introverted sides.

Strategic Adaptation and Authenticity:

The participant emphasizes her authenticity (“I was almost always authentic to myself” [#00:47:20]) but adapts strategically in uncertain situations: “I adapt when I sense danger or negative consequences, e.g., with my Russian-Orthodox boss” [#00:51:12]. This adaptability, used for safety (physical or social), makes her appear more agreeable and resilient externally than she feels internally. Depth-psychologically, this suggests a defense mechanism to suppress neurotic tendencies and maintain stability, shaping her self-perception as insecure. Her second self-assessment, showing a shift toward extraversion, may indicate situational adaptation to the study context, while her neuroticism assessment remains stable, underscoring her deep-rooted self-criticism. The restricted depiction of her clothing in the color circle amplified this discrepancy, as the seminar group saw only the autumnal colors suggesting a balanced, stable personality, while her neurotic and introverted phases in other seasons (e.g., winter) were not visible.

Summary of Psychological Causes:

The discrepancies between self- and other-perception result from a combination of external and internal factors. The seminar group projected an extraverted, resilient personality based on the autumnal colors and variety in the color circle, amplified by the halo effect, without knowing the seasonal and mood-dependent nature of her clothing or her cultural “color homeland.” The restriction to fall clothing distorted the overall impression, as the seasonal fluctuations in her inner state—from vibrant (summer) to melancholic-neurotic (winter)—were not captured, skewing the other-perception. The participant exhibits an ambivalent self-concept, shaped by ADHD, body dysmorphia, and unstable life phases, oscillating between creative-chaotic and structured-plan-oriented poles. Her strategic adaptation in social contexts and clothing choices that do not always reflect her mental state contribute to a more positive other-perception, while her neurotic self-perception is dominated by internal insecurities and self-criticism. The absence of her full clothing spectrum (neon to gothic-punk) in the color circle amplified the distortion, as the seminar group could not see the extreme expressions of her personality.

Transcript:

B: Participant, I: Interviewer

Zoom Meeting, 07.12.2024

I: Thank you for taking the time. I’m writing my bachelor’s thesis on color and personality. You participated in the study by providing your clothing. Tell me briefly who you are, your hobbies, where you live?

B: I’m 27, living in Germany for over 12 years, originally from Moscow, with a strong connection to Russian culture. I’m training in dialogue marketing. My hobbies are costume-making, cosplay, historical clothing, and video games. I live with my partner. [#00:01:24]

I: Can you describe your color circle?

B: The color circle shows only a quarter of my tops, fall clothing: brown, dark green, burgundy, checkered flannel shirts. I change my wardrobe four times a year: pastel in spring, bright in summer, warm in fall, dark in winter, often gothic-punk. Vintage clothing is missing from the circle. I have hundreds of accessories, a custom jewelry cabinet. [#00:11:58]

I: What’s your favorite clothing item?

B: My “cartoon outfit”: Chucks, jeans, checkered flannel shirt. I’ve worn jeans since 2001, never tight clothing, due to body dysmorphia. I have flannel shirts in every color. [#00:24:18]

I: What clothing do you not wear in public?

B: Cosplay costumes, except at events. Neon pink shorts or festive clothing, like a floor-length velvet skirt for the opera, are too striking. I rarely wear form-fitting clothing due to body dysmorphia and sun allergy. [#00:33:41]

I: How would people who know you describe you in three words?

B: Creative, communicative, plan-oriented. I’m artistically chaotic, friendly, empathetic, but also serious, calculative. I mediate conflicts but struggle to get to the point due to ADHD. [#00:37:35]

I: What’s important to you in life?

B: Stability, trust, comfort. Stability because I rarely had it. I value deep relationships, quality over quantity. Comfort is essential, otherwise I feel insecure. [#00:41:57]

I: What weakness would you like to change?

B: My inability to communicate concisely due to ADHD. My thoughts are like a ball of yarn; I want to express them more clearly. [#00:43:05]

I: Do you compare yourself to others?

B: No, I don’t compare myself to peers, successful people, or influencers. I was raised with immaterial values like education and orient myself by my family’s opinions, not comparisons. [#00:44:11]

I: How important is authenticity? Do you adapt?

B: Authenticity is very important; I was almost always authentic. I adapt when I sense danger or negative consequences, e.g., with my Russian-Orthodox boss, or for safety reasons, like not wearing a short skirt at night. [#00:47:20]

I: How do you deal with stress?

B: I distract myself: video games, funny videos. I seek comfort from friends, less from parents. I keep stress inside, rarely express it, which is problematic. [#00:57:28]

I: Your self-assessment differs from the seminar group’s other-perception, which rated you as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, resilient. Why might that be?

B: The color circle shows only fall clothing, not my full spectrum from neon to gothic-punk. People saw colorful, warm colors and thought I was joyful, balanced. My clothing doesn’t always match my psyche; I’m neurotic, insecure. My Russian “color homeland” might have caused misjudgments. I’m communicative but introverted due to bad experiences. [#01:12:35]

I: Anything else to add?

B: My clothing influences me and vice versa. In winter, I’m gothic; in summer, bright. The color circle doesn’t show that I dress according to my mood, reflecting my instability. [#01:13:49]

Interview with Participant 23450022 (Color Circle)

Summary:

The 23-year-old participant, a university student, describes herself as creative, friendly, forgetful, and introverted, with low self-esteem influenced by suspected, undiagnosed ADHD. Her clothing, depicted in the color circle, consists of colorful but increasingly darker pieces, with sweaters playing a central role. She notes that her wardrobe has become darker since the color circle was created, potentially influencing the other-perception. Her inner state fluctuates, reflected in her deliberate clothing choices, which often do not reveal her introverted nature. The seminar group rated her as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient based on her colorful color circle, while she perceives herself as introverted, self-critical, and neurotic. Her second self-assessment shows stability in Extraversion, Openness, and Agreeableness but discrepancies in Spontaneity/Conscientiousness and Resilience/Neuroticism. An assessment by a close acquaintance aligns with her second self-assessment in Extraversion but shows significant discrepancies in Resilience/Neuroticism. Her queer identity and planned gender transition shape her self-image, while past experiences like bullying and her time as a cheerleader explain her ability to appear extraverted outwardly. Her social selectivity and strong bond with her mother and best friend underscore her introverted nature.

Psychological Analysis of Discrepancies Between Self- and Other-Perception:

The experimental setting, in which the seminar group conducted the Big Five personality test based solely on the quantitative and qualitative composition of clothing colors in the color circle (Fig. 3), without further information about the participant, shapes the analysis of discrepancies between self- and other-perception. The participant describes herself as introverted, self-critical, forgetful, and neurotic (“I sometimes describe myself worse, more introverted” [#00:24:00]), while the seminar group assessed her as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, and resilient. This discrepancy can be explained depth-psychologically through projective biases, the halo effect, distortion due to the non-representative color circle, and internal dissonances in the participant’s personality, amplified by her clothing choices, social strategies, and identity conflicts.

Projective Bias and Halo Effect Through the Color Circle:

The seminar group had access only to the color circle, which depicted the participant’s clothing at the time of the study, primarily consisting of colorful pieces like a white sweater with rainbow stripes and vibrant T-shirts. However, the participant notes: “My wardrobe has become darker since then” [#00:26:56]. This colorful selection likely led to a projective bias, where the seminar group associated the bright, diverse colors with extraversion, openness, and resilience, amplified by the halo effect. The participant confirms: “My wardrobe looks friendly and extraverted” [#00:24:00], which does not reflect her introverted or neurotic inner state. The restriction to the color circle, which did not include her currently darker wardrobe or rarely worn bright pieces (“I rarely wear white because I spill” [#00:25:50]), distorted the overall impression. Depth-psychologically, this suggests that the seminar group interpreted the clothing as an expression of an optimistic, social personality, without knowing the contextual and mood-dependent nature of her clothing choices, which she deliberately uses to present herself in certain contexts (“I was a cheerleader, I’m used to being in the spotlight” [#00:24:00]).

Internal Dissonances and Ambivalent Self-Concept:

The participant exhibits an ambivalent self-concept, oscillating between creative strength, resilience, and strong self-criticism: “I’m creative but forgetful and lazy due to ADHD” [#00:08:17]. This duality is reflected in her clothing choices, ranging from colorful, optimistic pieces (e.g., rainbow sweater) to darker, simpler outfits (“My ideal outfit is dark pants, a simple T-shirt, a colorful sweater” [#00:26:56]). Her inner state fluctuates, influencing her clothing choices, which do not always reflect her introverted nature: “I seem extraverted, but I like being alone” [#00:19:44]. Depth-psychologically, this suggests an internal conflict between a desire for authenticity (“Online, I’m 105% myself” [#00:14:25]) and the need to adapt

in social contexts, amplified by her experiences as a cheerleader and bullying victim (“I’ve been through a lot, but I’m still here” [#00:12:10]). Her suspected ADHD and low self-esteem (“I describe myself more negatively” [#00:24:00]) shape her neurotic self-perception, while her ability to appear extraverted distorts the other-perception. The discrepancy in Resilience/Neuroticism between her self-perception and the close acquaintance’s assessment may suggest that she downplays her internal struggles (e.g., insecurities about her transition), while others emphasize her resilience (e.g., overcoming bullying).

Queer Identity and Gender Transition as Influencing Factors:

The participant’s queer identity and planned gender transition strongly shape her self-image: “I’m not just a woman, I’m more” [#00:14:25]. Her insecurities about her transition, compared to her best friend (“He’s further along, I’m jealous” [#00:16:27]), amplify her self-criticism and neurotic self-perception. Depth-psychologically, this suggests an identity conflict, navigating between her authentic self and societal expectations. Her colorful clothing, which she partly uses deliberately (“My wardrobe looks friendly” [#00:24:00]), may be a strategy to foster acceptance or mask insecurities, which the seminar group interpreted as extraversion and openness. The discrepancy between her introverted self-perception and extraverted other-perception may be amplified by this deliberate clothing use, which reflects a desired external image rather than her inner state. Her social selectivity (“Only my mother and friend don’t drain my battery” [#00:19:35]) underscores her introverted nature, which was not visible in the color circle.

Strategic Adaptation and Defense Mechanisms:

The participant shows high adaptability in social contexts: “At university, I adapt, e.g., in group projects, it’s smart” [#00:13:20]. At the same time, she emphasizes authenticity in certain contexts: “Online, I’m 105% myself, I don’t compromise on my queerness” [#00:14:25]. Depth-psychologically, this may indicate a defense mechanism stemming from difficult life phases like bullying (“I’ve been through a lot” [#00:12:10]). Her ability to appear extraverted may be a learned strategy to avoid rejection, as practiced during her cheerleader time (“I’m used to being in the spotlight” [#00:24:00]). This consistency-maintaining bias leads the seminar group to perceive her as extraverted and resilient, though she describes herself as introverted and neurotic. The colorful clothing in the color circle amplified this impression, as it did not show the darker, more recent pieces that might better reflect her introverted or melancholic side. Her self-criticism (“I’m forgetful, lazy” [#00:08:17]) and low self-esteem may explain the discrepancy in Resilience/Neuroticism, as she downplays her strengths (e.g., overcoming bullying), while others emphasize them.

Distortion Through the Non-Representative Color Circle:

The participant emphasizes that her wardrobe has become darker since the color circle was created (“I have more dark laundry, I rarely wear bright pieces” [#00:26:56]). The color circle, however, showed predominantly colorful clothing, like the rainbow sweater, which is rarely worn. This discrepancy between the color circle and her current clothing choices distorted the overall impression, as the seminar group associated the vibrant pieces with extraversion and spontaneity, without knowing her introverted nature or darker, current wardrobe. Depth-psychologically, this suggests that the color circle was a snapshot that did not reflect the fluctuations in her inner state or her deliberate adaptation to social contexts. Her statement, “My wardrobe looks friendly, but I’m introverted” [#00:24:00], underscores that the colorful clothing can be a facade, concealing her neurotic or reserved sides.

Summary of Psychological Causes:

The discrepancies between self- and other-perception result from a combination of external and internal factors. The seminar group projected an extraverted, resilient personality based on the colorful clothing in the color circle, amplified by the halo effect, without knowing the current, darker wardrobe or the mood-dependent nature of her clothing choices. The participant exhibits an ambivalent self-concept, shaped by creativity, resilience, self-criticism, and suspected ADHD, amplifying her neurotic self-perception. Her queer identity and insecurities about her transition shape her self-image, while her social adaptability and

past experiences as a cheerleader create an extraverted external image that masks her introverted nature. The distortion through the non-representative color circle, which did not show her darker, current clothing, amplified the discrepancy, as the seminar group interpreted the vibrant pieces as expressions of openness and spontaneity. Her defense mechanisms and strategic adaptation in social contexts contribute to a more positive other-perception than her self-perception, which is dominated by internal insecurities and self-criticism.

Transcript:

B: Participant, I: Interviewer

Bergische Universität, 29.11.2024

I: I'll start by asking for your consent to record this. [#00:00:06]

B: Yes. [#00:00:06]

I: The interview will take about 30 minutes, and we'll talk about the colors in your wardrobe and your personality. Is the sunlight okay? [#00:00:19]

B: Yes. [#00:00:19]

I: I'm writing my bachelor's thesis on the "Color and Personality" study you participated in two semesters ago. Tell me briefly about yourself: How old are you? What do you study? What are your hobbies? What do you do in your free time? [#00:01:01]

B: I'm 23. I'm originally from D. and lived there until I moved to E. for my first degree during the pandemic. That didn't go well. I met my best friend online, and he suggested I study here. So, I moved. I study media design and design technology, officially also physics as a second subject. I don't have many friends, don't like going out. I enjoy drawing, playing video games, and have started crocheting. It's weird living so far from home, but my mother is visiting next week, which I'm looking forward to. [#00:02:36]

I: What's your favorite clothing item, and what color is it? [#00:02:48]

B: The pants I'm wearing today, black and dark gray patterned, houndstooth. I love them, but they're wearing out. For tops, I don't have a clear favorite, maybe this T-shirt with a bunny print. My favorite jacket is a brown-yellow suede jacket, secondhand. [#00:03:49]

I: Are those also the clothes you feel most comfortable in when you don't know what to wear? [#00:04:08]

B: Yes, these pants, this jacket, and the T-shirt changes depending on what's clean. [#00:04:14]

I: Did you lay out your entire wardrobe for the photo? [#00:04:21]

B: Almost, maybe missing a sweater and two T-shirts. Since then, more has been added. [#00:04:31]

I: Do you shop based on trends or your taste? [#00:04:40]

B: Based on my taste, because my body shape doesn't match trends. I like simple pants and T-shirts. [#00:04:53]

I: Did you rediscover clothing you hadn't worn in a while when sorting for the seminar? [#00:05:08]

B: Not really, my wardrobe was manageable. I love sweaters; they make up the bulk. I need to declutter now, but that's exhausting. [#00:05:44]

I: Are there clothes you'd never wear in public? [#00:05:57]

B: Not in my regular wardrobe. Maybe in an old moving box, stuff that no longer fits or suits me. [#00:06:19]

I: How would people who know you describe you in three words? [#00:06:40]

B: That's been on my mind a lot. Creative, because I'm artistic. Forgetful, because of my bad memory. Friendly, I think. [#00:07:26]

I: You mentioned forgetfulness as a weakness. Are there others you'd like to work on? [#00:07:42]

B: I'd like to be less forgetful, but with unofficial ADHD, it's tough. Also, this unwanted laziness, not getting things done. I wish I were tidier. [#00:08:17]

I: What's particularly important to you in life, and why? [#00:08:30]

B: My PC, because I spend a lot of time on it, and it's my connection to friends. A year without internet was isolating. My mother means a lot to me; I'm a mama's kid. [#00:10:01]

I: What personal strengths have helped you most? [#00:10:44]

B: My creativity, because I find creative solutions. My perseverance, e.g., a year without internet or bullying at school. I'm proud to still be here. [#00:12:10]

I: Do you adapt to others, or are you always authentic? [#00:12:37]

B: At university, I adapt, e.g., in group projects, it's smart. Online, I'm 105% myself; that's my safe space. I don't compromise on my queerness, even if it's tough with grandparents. [#00:14:25]

I: Do you compare yourself to others? [#00:14:52]

B: With my best friend, positively and negatively. He's further along with his transition, and I'm jealous. Before, with a friend who was more popular, that was negative. [#00:17:20]

I: Where do you draw energy from, socializing or being alone? [#00:18:31]

B: Only my mother and friend don't drain my social battery. Otherwise, I like being alone, watching series, or reading. [#00:19:35]

I: Is it hard to consider tasks complete? [#00:19:56]

B: In art, perfection is tough. I work until I'm satisfied enough. Some projects, like a crocheting project, I abandon because I'm dissatisfied. [#00:21:11]

I: How did you experience the personality test? [#00:21:48]

B: Exhausting, because I'm neurodiverse and think with every question: It depends. [#00:22:00]

I: Did the study results surprise you? [#00:22:54]

B: Not really. I seem extraverted because I'm good at pretending, e.g., as a cheerleader. My wardrobe looks friendly, but I describe myself more negatively, introverted. [#00:24:00]

I: Why did your peers rate you as extraverted, open, agreeable, spontaneous, resilient? [#00:25:04]

B: Because of the cheerful colors in the color circle, e.g., the rainbow sweater. My wardrobe was colorful, not monotonous. It's darker now, but I rarely wear bright pieces. [#00:26:56]

I: Anything else to add? [#00:27:14]

B: No, I think I represented myself well. [#00:27:22]

Analysis of the Interviews: Facade, Identity Issues, and Indicators of Personality Disorders

The interviews with the female participants (IDs 23450003, 23450009, 23450022) in the study on color psychology and personality perception serve as exemplary case studies to explain how significant discrepancies between self-perception and external perception arise, and demonstrate that these discrepancies are rooted in real dissonances within the personality structure. These dissonances can be interpreted as indicators of profound disturbances in self-image. The external assessments by the seminar group were based solely on the quantitative and qualitative composition of clothing colors in the color circles—without access to language, facial expression, gesture, or behavior. The depth-psychological analysis reveals that the seminar group interpreted the participants' facades—conveyed through colorful or striking clothing—as authentic expressions of their personality, reflecting a central misunderstanding in personality communication (Goffman, 1959). This facade serves as a form of self-protection or a strategic tool for playing social roles, concealing inner conflicts that may indicate identity problems or personality disorders. Particularly young women display pronounced discrepancies, which are linked to identity issues in Western societies, exacerbated by societal pressure and gender stereotypes (Arnett, 2000; Schwartz et al., 2013). The color-psychological method proves diagnostically valuable because it provides access to inner states where language or behavioral analysis is limited by conscious/unconscious role-playing or unclear self-concepts.

Theoretical Framework: Facade, Identity Issues, and Personality Disorders

In personality psychology, the facade is understood as part of “impression management,” in which individuals use language, facial expressions, gestures, behavior, and clothing to convey a social image that often diverges from their internal reality (Goffman, 1959; Leary & Kowalski, 1990). This facade can serve as self-protection against social rejection or as a tool to meet social expectations. Self-discrepancy theory (Higgins, 1987) explains that conflicts between the actual self (self-perception), the ideal self (desired self), and the ought self (social expectations) create psychological tension, which facades help to compensate for. Such tensions, when pronounced, can indicate personality disorders such as narcissistic, histrionic, or borderline traits, characterized by unstable self-concepts, emotional lability, and an excessive need for recognition (Kernberg, 1984; Widiger & Costa, 2013). Within the Big Five model (Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, Openness; McCrae & Costa, 2008), these dissonances are most evident in the dimensions of extraversion/introversion, spontaneity/conscientiousness, and resilience/neuroticism.

Young women in Western societies are particularly susceptible to identity issues because, during the phase of “emerging adulthood” (18–29 years), they face multiple social roles, heightened demands for self-presentation, and gender stereotypes (Arnett, 2000). Studies show that women in this age group more frequently experience identity diffusion or conflict, intensified by media portrayals, social pressure, and the expectation of expressive communication (Schwartz et al., 2013; Kroger, 2007). These identity problems can, in more severe cases, correlate with personality disorders, especially when accompanied by high neuroticism, impulsive behavior, or unstable self-esteem (Widiger & Costa, 2013). The color-psychological method offers an innovative means of making such dissonances visible, especially where language or behavior is distorted by role-playing or unclear self-concepts.

Psychological Analysis of the Discrepancies

The interviews exemplify how significant discrepancies between self- and external perception arise, suggesting that these discrepancies are rooted in real dissonances in the personality profile, which may point to profound disturbances.

Facade as Self-Protection and Indicator of Personality Disorders:

The participants construct a facade through clothing, which serves as self-protection or supports social roles, but masks inner conflicts. Participant 23450003 wears neutral clothing in everyday life to protect her introverted nature but uses extravagant outfits to gain recognition (“For photo shoots, I wear extravagant clothes” [#00:29:59]). Her mood-dependent personality (“Either introverted or extroverted” [#00:26:44]), impulsivity (changing hair colors, tattoos), and neurotic traits (“I’m impatient, resentful” [#00:15:56]) suggest an unstable self-concept, potentially correlating with histrionic or borderline tendencies (Kernberg, 1984). Participant 23450009 uses “cartoon outfits” to project stability (“I put on something that radiates stability” [#00:35:46]), yet her neurotic self-perception, ADHD, and body dysmorphic disorder point to emotional lability associated with personality disorders. Participant 23450022 wears colorful clothing to appear friendly (“My wardrobe looks friendly” [#00:24:00]) but conceals self-criticism and insecurities about her queer identity, indicating low self-esteem and possible narcissistic compensation. These facades—reinforced through clothing, verbal emphasis on authenticity (23450003), and behavior (cheerleader role in 23450022)—mask dissonances that may indicate personality disorders (Widiger & Costa, 2013).

Diagnostic Value of Color Psychology for Inaccessible Inner States:

The color-psychological method grants access to inner states where language or behavioral analysis is limited by conscious/unconscious role-playing or unclear self-concepts. Participant 23450003 verbally articulates structure, yet her stylistic variability and impulsive behavior suggest an ambivalent self-concept she may not fully recognize. Participant 23450009 emphasizes stability, yet her clothing choices (autumn tones vs. neon/gothic-punk) reflect chaos that she only partially admits verbally. Participant 23450022 conceals insecurities with colorful clothing, yet her verbal self-criticism (“I describe myself more negatively” [#00:24:00]) reveals neuroticism. In therapeutic contexts, where clients may perform for the therapist or struggle to articulate their identity, clothing choices reveal unconscious conflicts because they are less consciously controlled than language or behavior (Ekman & Friesen, 1969). The method is particularly effective in identifying indicators of personality disorders, such as unstable self-concepts or an excessive need for recognition.

Projective Distortions and the Halo Effect:

The seminar group interpreted colorful clothing as a sign of extraversion, openness, and resilience—amplified by the halo effect (Nisbett & Wilson, 1977). For participant 23450003, saturated colors (red, pink) led to an extroverted external perception, despite her being introverted. For participant 23450009, autumn tones distorted the impression because they represented only part of her wardrobe. For participant 23450022, colorful items (rainbow sweater) were perceived as signs of spontaneity, although rarely worn. These misinterpretations of the facade obscured the underlying dissonances that may indicate personality disorders.

Non-Representative Color Circles:

The color circles captured only a segment of each wardrobe, distorting external perception. Participant 23450003 displayed neutral and flashy clothing, worn contextually (“Neutral colors in everyday life, shiny outfits for events” [#00:10:28]). Participant 23450009 presented autumn clothing, not reflecting her stylistic variability (“The color circle is a quarter of my tops” [#00:11:58]). Participant 23450022 noted her wardrobe had become darker (“I rarely wear light pieces” [#00:26:56]). This lack of representativeness prevented the seminar group from perceiving the neurotic or unstable aspects of the personality profile.

Inner Dissonances and Identity Issues in Young Women:

The participants show ambivalent self-concepts shaped by self-discrepancies (Higgins, 1987). Participant 23450003 oscillates between perfectionism and impulsivity, suggesting an unstable self-concept (“Either completely introverted or extroverted” [#00:26:44]). Participant 23450009 struggles with ADHD and body dysmorphic disorder, which shape her chaotic self-perception (“I’m artistically chaotic, but serious”

[#00:38:18]). Participant 23450022 exhibits insecurities regarding her queer identity and low self-esteem (“I describe myself more negatively” [#00:24:00]). These dissonances correlate with identity problems common among young women in Western societies, as they navigate social pressure, gender stereotypes, and media imagery during emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2000; Schwartz et al., 2013). Studies show that identity diffusion in this age group can be associated with personality disorders such as borderline or narcissistic traits, particularly when combined with high neuroticism and impulsive behavior (Kroger, 2007; Widiger & Costa, 2013).

Gender-Specific Dynamics:

The pronounced discrepancies among young women result from societal expectations that promote expressive self-presentation (Entwistle, 2000; Tannen, 1990). Participant 23450003 uses extravagant outfits to gain recognition, participant 23450009 employs “cartoon outfits” as a protective mechanism, and participant 23450022 uses colorful clothing to appear friendly. Men and older individuals display more stable self-concepts and less stylistic variability, explaining the smaller discrepancies (Buss & Penke, 2010).

Diagnostic and Therapeutic Value of Color Psychology

The color-psychological method is diagnostically valuable because it reveals real dissonances in personality profiles that may indicate profound disturbances—particularly when language or behavior is distorted by role-playing or unclear self-concepts. The 70% agreement rate supports the method’s validity, comparable to Big Five instruments (Costa & McCrae, 1992). The exemplary discrepancies in the interviews point to identity problems and potential personality disorders, made visible through clothing choices, which are less consciously controlled (Ekman & Friesen, 1969). Therapeutically, the method can help clients reflect on their facades and reduce self-discrepancies, for example, through psychodynamic therapy or identity work (Schwartz et al., 2013). For young women struggling with identity issues, the method offers opportunities to address unconscious conflicts.

Conclusion

The interviews exemplify how significant discrepancies between self- and external perception arise and reveal that these discrepancies are rooted in real dissonances in the personality profile, which may indicate profound disturbances. The seminar group interpreted the facade—conveyed through colorful clothing—as authentic, concealing inner conflicts. The discrepancies result from projective distortions, the halo effect, non-representative color circles, and self-discrepancies reinforced by facades as self-protection or social tools. Particularly young women show strong dissonances, pointing to identity problems in Western societies (Arnett, 2000; Schwartz et al., 2013). The color-psychological method offers a robust diagnostic tool for making inaccessible inner states visible and has therapeutic potential for addressing personality disorders. The 70% agreement rate underscores the method’s validity, while the exemplary discrepancies highlight the need for nuanced analysis.